

Process and procedures report based on the concrete use cases

Deliverable D4.1

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Acronyms.

Acronym	Meaning
A2A	Authority-to-Authority
ADR	"European Agreement concerning the International Carriage of Dangerous Goods by Road" and refers to the French "Accord Européen Relatif au Transport international des marchandises dangereuses par route"
AETR	European Agreement Concerning the Work of Crews of Vehicles Engaged in International Road Transport
ANPR	Automatic Number Plate Recognition
API	Application Programming Interface
CMRs	"Convention on the Contract for the International Carriage of Goods by Road" and refers to the French "Convention relative au contrat de transport international de marchandises par route"
CPC	Driver Certificate of Professional Competence
CRIS	Croatian Road Inspection System
D	Deliverable (of the KEYSTONE project)
DTLF	Digital Transport and Logistics Forum
DSRC	Dedicated Short-Range Communication
EC	European Commission
e-CMR	Electronic version of Convention on the Contract for the International Carriage of Goods by Road
eFTI	Electronic Freight Transport Information
eFTI4EU	Electronic Freight Transport Information for the European Union
ERRU	European Registers of Road Transport Undertakings
EU	European Union
EUCARIS	European Car and Driving License Information System
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPS	Global Positioning System
GSIS	General Secretariat for Information Systems (Greece)
IMI	Internal Market Information System
IT	Information Technology
ITS	Intelligent Transport Systems
IRU	International Road Transport Union
MitID	"My Identity" in Danish. It is Denmark's national electronic identification system
NCP	National Contact Point
Pol	Digital application of Hellenic Police
PTI	Periodical Technical Inspection
PWD	Posting of Workers Directive
QR code	Quick Response code
REDCR	Remote Early Detection of Non-Compliance Risks

Acronym	Meaning
RESPER	RESeau PERmis de conduire (French); Driving Licences Network
RSI	Roadside Inspection
RTM	Remote Tachograph Monitoring
SME	Small and Medium-Sized Enterprise
STD	Sistema Telematico Doganale (Italian)
T	Task (of the KEYSTONE project)
TACHOnet	“Tachograph Network” a Digital Card Verification System
TachoScan	software tool designed for control authorities to analyse drivers' working time data
VaDIS	Vehicle and Driver Inspection System (Norway digital roadside inspection tool)
WP	Work Package (of the KEYSTONE project)

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1. Executive Summary.

Transport plays a vital role in the European Union's economy, supporting millions of jobs and enabling the smooth movement of goods and people. The transition to telematic documentation through electronic platforms is essential for managing freight efficiently, securely, and transparently. The adoption of EU Regulation 2020/1056 on electronic Freight Transport Information (eFTI) represents a key milestone in the EU's efforts to digitalise freight transport. The KEYSTONE project is aligned with the EU's vision for a modern, secure, and sustainable transport ecosystem, contributing to the resilience and competitiveness of the internal market. Deliverable 4.1 of the KEYSOTNE project outlines the findings of Task 4.1 under Work Package 4 (WP4) – Piloting, which focuses on the development and implementation of demonstration scenarios during Phase 5. These pilots aim to define implementation procedures and showcase the feasibility of KEYSTONE solutions within both digital road transport ecosystem (Pilot 1) and digital intermodal ecosystem (Pilot 2). Task 4.1 evaluates existing enforcement procedures and the operational feasibility of pilots for law enforcement authorities, particularly the police. The Deliverable 4.1 examines the needs and requirements of enforcement authorities (Chapter 3).

Earlier phases of the KEYSTONE project, particularly under Work Package 1 (WP1) – “Gap Analysis and State of the Art,” assessed the current transport enforcement landscape and identified key gaps between stakeholder needs and the capabilities of existing digital systems. To gain a deeper understanding of enforcement operations and challenges, Task 4.1 included the design and dissemination of a comprehensive questionnaire. This tool, collaboratively developed and validated by consortium partners, was distributed to enforcement authorities across 33 European countries. Chapter 4 of the deliverable presents a detailed analysis of the responses, revealing critical insights into cross-border logistics enforcement challenges.

The findings from Task 4.1 (Chapter 5) underscore the urgent need to improve access to transport data, advance digital enforcement processes, and strengthen cross-border cooperation. Although most countries implement annual National Enforcement Plans and make use of technologies such as digital tachographs and remote enforcement tools, issues persist. Digital platforms like IMI, TACHOnet, EUCARIS, and ERRU are commonly used, yet enforcement is hindered by system fragmentation, varied levels of access, and inconsistent response times. Key barriers include complex and disjointed systems, limited database access, lack of harmonisation in data formats across Member States and insufficient training. Verification practices differ widely, ranging from visual inspections to digital checks, with limited and uneven access to cross-border data. Approximately half of the respondents still rely on both paper-based and digital processes, while operational challenges such as document retrieval delays, insufficient real-time truck flow data, and jurisdictional limitations remain widespread.

Authorities have clearly articulated the need for a centralized, digital, secure, and legally compliant platform to unify enforcement efforts. Such a system must enable integrated, real-time access to transport data related to vehicles, drivers, cargo, and companies. Authorities recommend that KEYSTONE platform be designed to meet these needs, serving as a multilingual, mobile-accessible, single-entry interface that consolidates existing systems and automates data cross-referencing. It should also facilitate real-time communication, digital document storage, vehicle tracking, and compliance alerting, while generating certified reports for legal use. By improving access, ensuring regulatory compliance, and fostering interoperability, KEYSTONE is expected to have the potential to transform enforcement practices, enhance cross-border cooperation, and contribute to a more efficient and secure EU transport system.

2. Introduction.

Transport plays a crucial role in European Union's economy, with 1.3 million public and private companies employing 10.2 million people and facilitating the movement of goods and services across the region. Transport also ensures connectivity, mobility and economic cohesion throughout Europe, contributing to the free movement of people and goods, as well as strengthening the competitiveness of the internal market. A well-functioning transport system that guarantees accessibility and efficiency is essential for fully leveraging the economic potential of all EU regions. Between 1995 and 2019, the volume of transported goods increased by 41%, while passenger transport grew by 33%, before experiencing a temporary decline due to the COVID-19 pandemic. (European Commission: Directorate-General for Mobility and Transport, 2024)

The transport sector faces increasing pressure from global challenges, such as climate change and disruptive crises, necessitating the adoption of innovative technologies and advanced mobility solutions to ensure long-term sustainability and resilience.

The logistics industry, in particular, is characterized by a high presence of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) that often lack the financial resources and information technology (IT) expertise necessary to invest in modern digital solutions. In contrast, a smaller number of large multinational companies operates with proprietary legacy IT systems, leading to significant inefficiencies and complexity in data exchange within the transport and logistics sectors. (Digital Transport and Logistics Forum (DTLF), 2018)

Effective data exchange is fundamental to ensuring smooth inspection and control processes. A major challenge remains the lack of real-time, accessible information on intermodal terminals and network capacities, which limits operational efficiency.

The use of telematic documentation via electronic platforms is essential for ensuring the efficient, secure, and traceable management of goods. Electronic platforms play a pivotal role in standardizing telematic documentation. Transitioning from paper-based processes to digital solutions offers numerous benefits for the transport and logistics sectors. It simplifies the storage and exchange of documents, making them easily accessible to all stakeholders involved—such as shippers, carriers, freight forwarders, terminals, ports, and authorities. This shift enhances security, improves traceability, and streamlines automation in the handling of goods during both reception and delivery processes.

Inspections serve a critical role in enforcing compliance with transport regulations and preventing fraudulent practices that could undermine the integrity of the sector. These compliance checks involve gathering, verifying, and analysing data on drivers, vehicles, operators, cargo, and the type of transport. Competent authorities—including port authorities, customs agencies, road police, etc.—must conduct these inspections either remotely or on-site by accessing specific databases—often shared by national authorities—that store the required documentation.

The KEYSTONE project aims to support the development of a sustainable, efficient, and secure transport system by providing competent authorities with seamless access to essential data. Through digitalized data exchange, the project seeks to enhance inspection and enforcement processes, reducing administrative burdens while ensuring compliance with EU transport regulations. Additionally, a comprehensive analysis of various use cases will offer valuable insights into the challenges and opportunities of freight transport operations.

The introduction of EU regulation 2020/1056 on electronic freight transport information (eFTI) represents a significant milestone in the digital transformation of freight transport across the European Union. This regulation establishes the legal framework for electronic information exchanges between economic operators and Member State authorities regarding the movement of cargo within the EU, delivering several key benefits: (European Commission: Directorate-General for Mobility and Transport, 2024)

- Reduced administrative costs in transport and logistics. According to the European Commission's estimates, the regulation could enable the industry to save between €20 billion and 27 billion over the period from 2018 and 2040, compared to a scenario without EU-level policy intervention. Additionally, this measure is projected to secure a reduction of 1.3 million tonnes of CO2 emissions during the same timeframe and cut congestion costs by nearly €300 million. Furthermore, it would save approximately 2 to 8 billion sheets of paper—or between 180,000 and 900,000 trees—annually. These savings are expected to positively impact the internal market by reducing costs for businesses. (European Parliament, 2020)
- Improved efficiency in the logistics chain. Digitalization will facilitate seamless information exchange between economic operators, streamlining operations across the sector.
- Enhanced enforcement of freight transport regulations. Standardized, high-quality data will enable risk-based controls, better monitoring, and more robust statistical analysis.

eFTI Regulation in practice – Vision

Figure 1. eFTI Regulation in practice—vision. (Villu Varjas, 2022)

Apostolos Tzitzikostas, Commissioner for Sustainable Transport and Tourism, emphasized the transformative potential of eFTI by stating: *"Europe's freight transport sector is preparing for the future. The introduction of Electronic Freight Transport Information is a big step forward, driving the digital transformation of our transport systems and improving efficiency. It could save the EU transport and logistics sector up to €1 billion per year. By creating common standards and making systems work together, eFTI paves the way for fully paperless transport in the EU."* (European Commission, 2025)

In this context, KEYSTONE represents a major opportunity for both businesses and enforcement authorities by enhancing transparency, efficiency, and cost-effectiveness in transport operations. The digitalization of information related to key entities—such as drivers, vehicles, operators, and cargo—will enable real-time, secure access to essential data. Moreover, adopting automated control mechanisms and analytical tools is vital for developing a modern, “plug-and-play” enforcement system that ensures regulatory compliance while streamlining administrative processes in road transport.

2.1 Objectives of the deliverable.

The objective of this deliverable is to compare existing enforcement procedures and assess the operability of pilot implementations for enforcement authorities, particularly the police.

The application of the plug-and-play concept within the digital transport ecosystem necessitates a thorough analysis of data-sharing processes to establish effective enforcement procedures. This task involves evaluating operational workflows and management processes, from the initial request for quotation to the final delivery of goods. Furthermore, it will ensure the automatic sharing of information with enforcement authorities, particularly control bodies such as police officers.

Currently, transport inspections often require vehicles to be stopped for manual document verification. However, an automated data-sharing process would enable authorities to remotely access transport documents, driving hours, and other relevant information in real time. This would significantly improve enforcement efficiency while minimizing disruptions to transport operations.

3. Enforcement authorities' needs and requirements.

3.1 Enforcement authorities: Key stakeholders in KEYSTONE.

Enforcement authorities, as crucial stakeholders in regulatory and logistical frameworks, serve diverse and vital functions in upholding laws and standards. Their scope and jurisdiction may vary based on the geographical area, type of regulation, and organizational structure, aligning with specific objectives and purposes.

Within the KEYSTONE framework, enforcement authorities play a pivotal role in coordination with other stakeholders, including logistics operators and freight terminals. These authorities ensure that operations within supply chains adhere to legal and regulatory requirements, facilitating seamless and compliant logistics.

Generally, an enforcement authority is any governmental or intergovernmental agency responsible for enforcing laws, regulations, and standards. Depending on their jurisdiction, enforcement authorities can operate:

- **Locally or Regionally:** Within a defined sub-national division, such as municipal or regional law enforcement.
- **Nationally:** Enforcing laws across an entire country.
- **Internationally:** Acting across borders or within multinational frameworks, as seen in organizations such as Interpol or the EU's Europol.

Furthermore, enforcement authorities can be classified into different types based on their function and focus: internal affairs, police forces, military, specialized agencies such as customs, taxation, or environmental protection, religious. Many authorities have dual responsibilities, enforcement and administrative, for example:

- **Customs Authorities:** Beyond enforcing trade regulations and preventing illegal imports/exports, they facilitate the movement of goods by offering streamlined services for legal trade.
- **Taxation Agencies:** While monitoring compliance with tax laws, they also provide guidance and systems for individuals and businesses to meet their obligations.
- **Environmental Agencies:** Enforcing environmental laws while promoting sustainable practices and providing support to industries in adhering to these regulations.

Enforcement authorities have their own specificities, needs and requirements. While the European Union enacts legislation to standardise regulations across its Member States, each country retains the autonomy to interpret and implement these rules independently. This autonomy inevitably creates challenges with interoperability, particularly when goods are transported across borders. Member States have developed national registers and databases, some of which are interconnected or partially accessible to the public.

Despite advancements at the national, European, and international levels, including the introduction of electronic registers, documents, and communication systems, enforcing compliance within the highly mobile road transport sector remains a significant challenge. The enforcement framework is widely regarded, even by those within the enforcement community, as being ineffective, inefficient, inconsistent, burdensome, and costly. Carriers and drivers often face financial losses and missed business opportunities due to prolonged, random, and unnecessary inspections. Meanwhile, enforcement authorities struggle with inadequate human, financial, and technical resources, making it difficult to ensure compliance with the complex regulatory framework effectively.

The growing internationalisation of road transport operations, coupled with the increasing complexity of transport regulations, has heightened the reliance on administrative cooperation between national authorities. Effective enforcement now depends more than ever on mutual assistance and the exchange of information concerning operators, drivers, vehicles, and the goods they transport. To support this cross-border collaboration, the European Union has developed several IT systems designed to enable secure Authority-to-Authority (A2A) communication and data exchange. Next table provides an overview of the most pertinent systems and their respective functions.

Table 1. Main IT system for the implementation of the EU road transport legislation (Source: Compiled by authors)

IT System	Function
TACHOnet	The TACHOnet is a telematic network in operation across the EU to allow an automated exchange of information between Member States. The Commission adopted on 21 January 2016 the Implementing Regulation (EU) No 2016/68 setting out the obligatory connection of Member States to TACHOnet by 2 March 2018, as well as the technical conditions for the use of TACHOnet. ¹
ERRU	ERRU (European Registers of Road Transport Undertakings), is an electronic system that allows Member States to exchange information on road transport companies. ERRU interconnects the national electronic registers on road transport undertakings of the different Member States, so that the competent authorities can mutually exchange information contained in their respective databases. ²
RESPER	RESPER is a telematic network to be established across the EU. It shall act as a hub for the exchange of information between national authorities responsible for issuing driving licences, in particular to guarantee recognition of documents and acquired rights originating in other Member States, combat document fraud and avoid the issuance of multiple licences. ³
IMI	The Internal Market Information System (IMI) is a secure, multilingual online tool that facilitates the exchange of information between public authorities involved in the practical implementation of EU law. It enables them to fulfil cross-border administrative obligations in multiple single market policy areas. ⁴
eFTI	The eFTI Regulation is set to transform freight transport within the EU by boosting efforts to replace paper-based documentation with electronic data in all transport modes. This digital shift will apply to road, rail, inland waterway, and air transport. It will reduce administrative burdens for operators and authorities, enhance data security, and ensure compliance with EU and national freight regulations. Authorities in all EU Member States will be required to accept electronic data when shared by businesses via eFTI-compliant platforms ⁵

¹ https://transport.ec.europa.eu/transport-modes/road/tachograph/tachonet_en

² https://transport.ec.europa.eu/transport-modes/road/rules-governing-access-profession/european-register-road-transport-undertakings-erru_en

³ <https://road-safety.transport.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-07/resper.pdf>

⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/internal_market/imi-net/about/index_en.htm

⁵ https://transport.ec.europa.eu/transport-themes/logistics-and-multimodal-transport/efti-regulation_en

Despite their benefits, these platforms have notable limitations. They do not consistently ensure accessibility, compatibility, or the secure and reliable exchange of data. Consequently, they often fall short of delivering significant efficiency improvements or easing the burden on authorities and logistics operators. Specifically, the methodologies and technologies currently in use by authorities lack the necessary interoperability and flexibility to address the evolving challenges of the logistics sector. Although electronic registers and documents have been introduced, much of the information remains in paper form, such as driving licences. It is estimated that 99% of cross-border transport operations in Europe still require at least one paper-based delivery note (CMR) during the journey (Concil of the European Union, 2021), meaning that only 1% of freight operations are conducted through fully digital information exchanges.

The limited access to comprehensive and reliable data on drivers, operators, vehicles, and goods significantly hampers the operational efficiency of enforcement authorities. Without sufficient contextual information, authorities are unable to conduct pre-emptive risk assessments regarding a vehicle's technical condition, a driver's non-compliance, or an operator's high-risk status. Consequently, only a small percentage of vehicles are inspected, with many being randomly selected for roadside checks. This random selection increases the likelihood that serious offenders may evade essential inspections, undermining the enforcement process. The complexity of the regulations governing mobility and transport further complicates the ability to monitor compliance effectively, presenting an ongoing challenge for enforcement authorities.

Furthermore, the platforms described above are not interconnected, requiring separate consultations to obtain a comprehensive view. Each platform has a unique interface and presents a learning curve for users. To enhance enforcement capabilities, the development of more advanced smart enforcement systems is necessary. Two models are currently under evaluation:

- **Centralized Model:** This model proposes a single access point for enforcement officers to connect with multiple information exchange systems, streamlining data retrieval.
- **Decentralized Model:** This model suggests the use of cloud-based infrastructure, enabling enforcement officers to access all relevant data regarding drivers, vehicles, operators, and cargo in a unified manner.

On January 9th, 2025, the European Commission took a significant step towards the digitalization of freight transport as the first eFTI implementing and delegated acts entered into force. The eFTI Regulation is an important step in the digital transformation of freight transport across the European Union. It creates the conditions for a shift from paper-based document exchanges to standardised electronic data on cargo transport for all transport modes.

The Table 2 presents the key benefits of implementing the eFTI Regulation for both businesses and enforcement authorities.

Table 2. Key benefits of eFTI Regulation. (European Commission)

For Businesses	For Authorities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transport operators will experience fewer unexpected stops and shorter delays caused by inspections. • The instant sharing of data through eFTI platforms will enable more efficient logistics planning, vehicle loading, and routing. • Businesses are projected to save up to EUR 13 per each consignment note. Annually, this could amount to EUR 1 billion in administrative cost savings for the EU transport and logistics sector. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simplified compliance checks will result in more targeted inspections and reduced inspection times. • Officers will be able to view information in their own language, thanks to automatic translation of the data shared electronically by businesses. • Information on electronically performed checks can be processed for monitoring and reporting purposes.

3.2 Overview of WP1 “Gap analysis and State of the Art” in relation to the needs of enforcement authorities.

The early stages of the KEYSTONE project focused on evaluating the current state of the art and identifying areas for improvement. Work Package 1 (WP1), title “Gap Analysis and State of the Art”, was dedicated to assessing the existing landscape and conducting a comprehensive gap analysis between stakeholders’ needs and the current state of digitalised transport systems. WP1 was structured into four main activities:

Task 1.1: Stakeholders’ identifications and needs (D1.1). The objective of this task was to map relevant stakeholders within the KEYSTONE project and identify their needs, current practices, regulatory requirements, barriers, and challenges. It specifically examined the use of digitalized transport ecosystems that enable intelligent and resilient transport operations.

To gather insights into the challenges and needs affecting cross-border logistics controls performed by enforcement authorities, a survey was designed and implemented. The survey focused on the following aspects:

- Type of data exchanged: Examining data shared with enforcement authorities and between participants in transport operations, such as logistics operators, transport companies, and freight terminals.
- Tools for data exchange: Assessing tools currently in use and the level of integration between national digital platforms and European systems.
- State of data sharing: Evaluating data-sharing practices between logistics actors and enforcement authorities, as well as among logistics stakeholders themselves.

By analysing these aspects, the survey provides a comprehensive overview of the current situation, highlighting both strengths and gaps in data sharing, digital tools, and platform integration. These insights are crucial for shaping the KEYSTONE project’s objectives and aligning them with the stakeholders’ requirements.

Task 1.2: Focus groups report including stakeholders' requirements and expectations (D1.2).

Through interviews and focus groups, this task studies the current state of the art while gathering stakeholder requirements necessary for developing KEYSTONE solutions.

Task 1.3: Needs and requirements for the future digital logistics ecosystem (D1.3).

This task involved a detailed evaluation of at least ten digital platforms used by various stakeholders, including enforcement authorities. A gap analysis was conducted to compare existing data exchange mechanisms with stakeholder needs.

Task 1.4: Digital ecosystem framework (D1.4).

Use cases are developed based on real-world transport ecosystems to reflect the specific contexts and requirements of both public and private stakeholders.

The WP1 targeted 36 enforcement authorities across 20 European countries. This diverse group encompassed various types of enforcement bodies, such as ministries, public authorities (including seaport authorities), road police, and customs agencies. The study also included other relevant organizations, such as federal offices responsible for drafting road traffic legislation, authorities designated by the Italian Transport Ministry for conducting checks on road and rail transport of all goods (including waste and dangerous goods), and user associations. Table 3 outlines the number of responses received, categorised by authority type and the corresponding countries where the authorities are based.

Table 3. Enforcement authorities: responses collected per authority type and corresponding countries. (WP1. D1.2. Focus Group report including stakeholder requirements and expectations)

Authority type	Number of answers	Countries
Ministry	12	Hungary, Croatia, Cyprus, Spain, Slovenia, Romania, the Netherlands, the United Kingdom.
Public authority (e.g. seaport authority)	9	Spain, Sweden, Italy, Malta, Portugal, Ireland.
Road Police	8	Belgium, Germany, Lithuania, the Netherlands, Poland, Spain.
Other (Authorities that do not identify themselves in the category predefined in the survey (category "Other")).	4	Spain, Switzerland, Italy, Greece.
Customs	3	Italy, Slovenia, France.

Key findings from the analysis of data collected regarding enforcement authorities in Work Package 1 include:

- **Data and technology:** 88% of respondents agreed that data and technology play a crucial role in improving and enhancing compliance checks.
- **Harmonisation of Legislation:** 12% of enforcement authorities emphasised the necessity of harmonising legislation across EU member states. Common challenges include: Geopolitical issues (e.g., Brexit, non-EU borders); Regulatory inconsistencies and shipment-specific complexities (e.g., hazardous or perishable goods); Language barriers and insufficient personnel training.
- **Need for Additional Data:** The survey revealed that 85% of enforcement authorities believe certain data not currently shared with them could be provided by stakeholders such as logistics operators, terminal or freight operators, and foreign authorities. Access to this data would significantly enhance the effectiveness of their checks. Specific needs include:

- Vehicle information and status. Details from recent Roadside Inspection (RSI) or Periodical Technical Inspection (PTI). This would prevent repeated RSI checks during a single journey and promote mutual recognition of PTI results across countries.
 - Data to combat fraud-related offenses more efficiently. This includes information to verify a vehicle's route up to the point of inspection (e.g., traffic records, shipping manifests, tolling data). For example, GPS tracking could corroborate tachograph data and identify manipulations.
 - Information on loads. Sharing shipping manifests containing information about passenger's details from incoming ferries could assist in profiling operators and targeting high-risk cases.
 - Load-related details: Information about cargo weight or type.
 - Operational data: Timesheets, driven distances, shipping orders.
 - Real-time traffic information: Roadblocks, estimated times of arrival, origin-destination data.
 - Terminal data: Waiting times, subcontracting numbers, transport pricing)
 - Data for customs risk-based inspections, information on Logistic Service Providers (LSPs) and shippers, planned driver stops, and travelled distances for carbon footprint calculations.
 - Cross-Border Data Sharing. Respondents emphasized the need for real time driving license data, operator licensing information, and data on transport practices and regulations across European countries.
- Digital Tools: 40% of respondents identified the lack of suitable digital tools for data sharing as a primary barrier, noting the absence of unified national or international platforms.
 - Platform Enhancement: 88% of respondents agreed that existing platforms should be improved and enhanced, primarily through the integration of new data sources.

A key aspiration is access to Europe-wide real-time transport data to facilitate instant roadside checks. This includes consistent information on foreign vehicles and drivers, comparable to domestic data sources such as tachograph card records, CPC card information, driver licensing details, and vehicle roadworthiness data.

Currently, 70% of authorities use EU-developed IT systems to support cross-border enforcement, including platforms such as ERRU, TACHOnet, Resper, IMI, and eFTI. However, survey respondents identified several areas for improvement:

- Integration: Consolidating multiple EU platforms into a single interface to provide seamless access to information.
- Accessibility: Enhancing the usability of platforms and improving the availability of data for roadside checks.
- Functionality: Simplifying processes and ensuring more comprehensive data sharing capabilities.

Implementing these improvements would significantly enhance the efficiency of enforcement authorities and facilitate more effective cross-border collaboration within the European Union.

3.3 Enforcement authorities work and needs: the “Enforcement Authority Feedback Survey”.

Enforcement authorities play a crucial role in ensuring compliance with regulations governing road transport logistics. Their primary responsibilities include monitoring the technical condition of vehicles, verifying driver compliance with working time directives, and ensuring the safe and secure transport of goods. These authorities conduct roadside inspections and checks at freight terminals to detect violations such as overloading, improper securing of cargo, or breaches of driving and rest time regulations. By fulfilling these responsibilities, enforcement authorities contribute to maintaining road safety, reducing environmental impact, and ensuring fair competition among transport operators.

The use of advanced technology, such as automated number plate recognition (ANPR) and electronic document verification, helps streamline the enforcement process and enhances the authorities' ability to conduct thorough and effective checks. Through their work, these authorities play a vital role in upholding the integrity of the EU's transport network and fostering a safe and efficient logistics sector.

To gain a deeper understanding of the work carried out by the enforcement authorities and to obtain first-hand knowledge of their needs, a questionnaire has been prepared. The primary goal is to identify key needs and obstacles that currently impact the work of enforcement authorities in logistics inspections.

The analysis of the results will highlight the key needs and challenges related to controls that stakeholders face daily in their operations.

3.3.1 Questionnaire targets.

The objective of this questionnaire is to examine the current practices employed by enforcement authorities in the European Union for collecting and verifying data on drivers, vehicles, and transport companies, both domestically and from other EU Member States. Specifically, it aims to assess the procedures currently used by these authorities when conducting checks.

To achieve this, the questionnaire is directed at enforcement authorities, including road police, customs officials, financial police, ministries, and other public entities.

3.3.2 “Enforcement Authority Feedback Survey” structure.

The questionnaire is designed to assess existing enforcement procedures. Its content and questions were collaboratively developed and validated by all members of the consortium, with significant contributions from those involved in WP4, "Pilot".

Following an introduction to the KEYSTONE project, the anonymous questionnaire is structured into four distinct sections, each focusing on a specific aspect:

- **Profiling:** general characteristics of the respondents (excluding sensitive data), such as their country and category of authority.
- **Control:** Information on enforcement activities, including regulatory frameworks, time allocation, and key resources used.

- **Digital platforms:** Assessment of current digital platforms, including connectivity, response times, challenges, barriers, and unmet user needs.
- **Data verification:** Methods and timing of data verification, as well as the primary challenges encountered.
- **Future Perspectives:** Identification of the most relevant data types, essential features and functionalities for KEYSTONE, and additional suggestions for improvement.

The full questionnaire is available in Annex 1.

3.3.3 “Enforcement Authority Feedback Survey” distribution & promotion.

To maximise the number of responses, the compilation period for the survey has been extended from the end of October 2024 to the end of March 2025. During this period, several reminders were sent to potential stakeholders/respondents, and biweekly updates were translated for partners to monitor and further disseminate the survey.

The questionnaire has been promoted through several channels:

- Emails sent to interested parties.
- News published on the KEYSTONE website
- News published on partners’ website
- Posts on social media platforms, primarily LinkedIn and X

Figure 2. News published on the KEYSTONE website

Shaping the Future of Mobility: AETHON's Vision in Action at the KEYSTONE EU Workshop

The KEYSTONE EU Project workshop we hosted in Athens was a pivotal moment in our journey toward AI-driven, sustainable, and efficient transport ecosystems. Bringing together leading experts, pioneering projects, and key industry players, we tackled the challenges of digitized, federated transport networks and explored solutions that will define the future of European mobility.

Over the course of two days, we held the General Assembly for the project, with an additional day dedicated to a workshop. During this time, we engaged with SETO, SEDEA, eFTI4EU, SOTAH-AFFINIS, and esteemed partners like Port of La Spezia, CERTH, DG Move International, ICOOR, TTS Italia, RINA, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Coventry University, and the Smart Transportation Alliance. These discussions reinforced the power of collaboration and innovation in shaping the next generation of transport and logistics.

This workshop marked an important milestone in our commitment to leading logistics and transport, and above all collaboration and interoperability innovation. While this update comes later than planned, our mission remains the same: to redefine transport, foster impactful partnerships, and drive Europe's mobility evolution.

Read more: https://lnkd.in/dpHp_hcg

Stay updated: https://lnkd.in/d9divc_w

And that's not all...

At AETHON, we believe in the power of collaboration. To continue our mission of shaping smarter, more efficient border enforcement systems, we encourage enforcement professionals across Europe to share their insights through the KEYSTONE Enforcement Authority Feedback Survey. Your input will play a crucial role in developing innovative solutions for cross-border data exchange and enhancing compliance processes.

Take the Survey Today: https://www.linkedin.com/posts/zoe-petrakou_keystone-survey-unveils-stakeholder-needs-activity-72878...

AETHON News and Tweets

We are a company of engineers who design innovative solutions for the cities and transportation system of the future

Live from #Industrytec 2025! We're at MEC Παλαιας, come chat about #AI, #automation & #smarttech. Let's connect! #SmartManufacturing #AETHONGR

Twitter

We're at #InnoventForum 2025! Visit our stand to chat about #AI, #innovation, and our #smartsolutions. See you at @joistpark, Feb 14-15! #Innovation #AI #FutureForward #AETHONGR

Twitter

Alex Papacharalampous, our CEO-CTO, says too many RDI projects fail because they ignore pilots. Is he right? Find out in his latest article! Read more: <https://shorturl.at/bzPJI> #Innovation #AETHONGR

Twitter

Figure 3. News published on partners website. (<https://aethon.gr/2025/02/17/aethon-keystone-eu-workshop-smart-mobility/>)

Figure 4. Post published on the KEYSTONE X.

Figure 5. Post published on LinkedIn

For the survey distribution, a list of potential stakeholders/respondents was compiled from various sources:

- Each KEYSTONE partner sent it to their network contacts.
- A list of key entities in each country, gathered from the website.

Table 4 lists the countries to which the “Enforcement Authority Feedback Survey” was distributed, either through direct contact via entities websites or by email to the main enforcement authorities.

Table 4. Countries to which the questionnaire was distributed.

• Albania	• Latvia
• Austria	• Liechtenstein
• Belgium	• Lithuania
• Bulgaria	• Luxembourg
• Croatia	• Malta
• Cyprus	• Netherlands
• Czech Republic	• Norway
• Denmark	• Poland
• Estonia	• Portugal
• Finland	• Romania
• France	• Slovakia
• Germany	• Slovenia
• Greece	• Spain
• Hungary	• Sweden
• Iceland	• Switzerland
• Ireland	• United Kingdom
• Italy	

3.3.4 “Enforcement Authority Feedback Survey” analysis. General statistics.

The questionnaire has been completed by 34 respondents located in 22 different European countries (Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland), as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Enforcement Authorities participating in D4.1: Map of countries headquarters

This group includes several types of enforcement authorities: ministries, public authorities (e.g. seaport authorities), road police, customs and others (authorities that do not identify themselves in the predefined category in the survey, classified as “Other”). The number of responses grouped by authority type and the corresponding countries of headquarters is displayed in Table 5.

Table 5. Enforcement authorities’ responses collected per authority type and corresponding countries.

Authority type	number of answers	Countries
Customs	2	Norway, Sweden
Ministry	5	Austria, Croatia, Estonia, Hungary, Switzerland
Public authority	10	Albania, Bulgaria, Denmark, Finland, Hungary, Ireland, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Norway
Road Police	14	Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Denmark, Estonia, Greece, Hungary, Latvia, Luxembourg, Portugal, Portugal, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland
Other	3	Greece, Poland, Slovakia

Compared to the data collection on law enforcement authorities conducted in WP1, Deliverable D4.1 has achieved greater representation of road police and public authorities, which were key priority objectives.

Notably, enforcement authorities from countries that had not participated in WP1 contributed to this phase, thereby complementing the information previously gathered. This broader participation has resulted in a more comprehensive understanding of enforcement and management procedures at the European level, as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Enforcement Authorities participating in KEYSTONE project: Map of countries headquarters

It is important to highlight that, on several occasions, responses received indicated a refusal to participate, primarily due to a lack of time and resources. In these cases, entities noted that they do not have the necessary human, time, or technical resources to provide a response.

Additionally, the non-participation of other entities may be attributed to various underlying factors, including:

- **Survey fatigue:** Respondents may have received numerous survey requests, leading to feelings of overload or disinterest in completing another one.
- **Perceived relevance:** Some respondents may feel that they have little or no valuable input to contribute.
- **Lack of incentives:** The perceived benefits or incentives for participation may not be compelling enough to justify their involvement.
- **Negative past experiences:** Previous encounters with overly complex, lengthy surveys or unclear outcomes may discourage participation.

The following chapter presents an analysis of the responses received. It is worth noting that while Albania provided a response, it only confirmed that the country is currently in the process of applying for membership in the RESPER, TACHONET, and ERRU platforms. As no further details were provided, Albania has not been included in the analysis conducted in the next chapter.

4. Enforcement procedures for transport control.

This section presents an analysis of the responses provided by participants to the "Enforcement Authority Feedback Survey." The objective of this analysis is to identify and gather insights into the key needs and challenges currently impacting the enforcement authorities' control activities in the field of road logistics.

4.1 The legislative framework.

The EU legal framework governing international commercial road transport services consists of a comprehensive set of legislative instruments aimed at harmonizing standards across the European Union. This framework is designed to ensure fair competition, enhance road safety, and regulate labour mobility for international transport drivers. Key provisions include regulations on driving and rest periods, the use of tachographs, cabotage operations, and the application of the Posting of Workers Directive (PWD) to the road transport sector. These legal instruments work in synergy to establish a robust regulatory structure that balances economic competitiveness with the protection of workers' rights and well-being.

At the national level, Member States are responsible for implementing and enforcing these EU regulations within their jurisdictions. National authorities, such as road police and customs agencies, play a crucial role in ensuring compliance with these rules.

This regulatory framework imposes significant demands on enforcement authorities, requiring them to adopt advanced enforcement practices, utilize digital platforms for data exchange, and align their strategies with EU harmonization efforts. Effective implementation of these regulations often necessitates cross-border cooperation, particularly in the enforcement of penalties. Additionally, it requires targeted investments in technology, comprehensive training for enforcement personnel, and the development of risk-based inspection methodologies to efficiently address non-compliance.

The EU legal framework not only facilitates the smooth functioning of the internal market but also ensures that enforcement authorities are equipped to uphold high standards of safety, equity, and regulatory compliance across the European Union. The primary objective of inspections is to strengthen compliance with existing regulations, prevent fraudulent activities that could undermine the integrity of road transport governance, and remove unsafe vehicles from circulation. To achieve this, enforcement measures must be rigorous and consistently applied. Systematic and well-structured road transport controls are essential to ensuring regulatory adherence and maintaining fair and safe transport operations.

As part of this framework, relevant entities were consulted to assess whether their respective countries have a National Plan outlining specific actions and guidelines for road inspections. Nearly all participating countries confirmed that they have an annual plan in place for this purpose. Table 6 provides a summary of the responses from each country.

Table 6. National legislative framework

Country	Does your country have a Road Transport Inspection Plan that establish actions and guidelines to follow during roadside inspection?
Austria	SVKO Basic Training Plan. Ministry of the Interior (Internal Guideline) This guideline generally applies to all heavy traffic vehicle inspection officers
Belgium	Not provided
Bulgaria	Plan of Preventive National Road Safety Campaigns in 2024. General Directorate of the National Police. Yearly plan. Annual Roadside Inspections Plan. General Directorate "Automobile Inspection". Yearly plan.
Croatia	Annual Work Plan of the Road Traffic Inspection. Ministry of the Sea, Transport and Infrastructure. Yearly plan.
Denmark	Tungvognshandlingsplan (Heavy Vehicle Action Plan). Central & West Zealand Police - The National Unit for Animal welfare and heavy vehicle. 4 years plan. Direktiv 2014-47-EU
Estonia	Road Transport Act, which outlines the responsibilities + Estonia aligns its roadside inspection practices with EU directives. Estonian Ministry of Climate/Estonian Transport Administration/Estonian Police and Border Guard Board. Frequency as needed.
Finland	Action Plan for Commercial Transports until 2030 (police). National Police Board. Yearly bases.
Greece	Not provided
Hungary	National Control Plan for the Road Transport Authorities. Ministry of Construction and Transport. Yearly plan.
Ireland	Compliance & Enforcement Policy & Road Safety Strategy. Road Safety Authority. Action plans typically span a period of 4-5 years.
Latvia	Procedures for the Organisation and implementation of Road traffic Control. Cabinet of Ministers Regulations No. 411. Government. Permanent Plan
Lithuania	Annual Road Checks Plan. Lithuanian Transport Safety Administration. Yearly plan.
Luxembourg	No. Currently, Luxembourg do not have a Road Transport Inspection Plan that clearly defines the actions to be taken and the guidelines to follow during road transport checks.
Netherlands	Regeling taken Dienst Wegverkeer (Directive 2014/47/EU). Dutch Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management. We act as supportive party to enforcement authorities.
Norway	Tverretatlig Transportkontroll. Road Authorities. Frequency: Regional controls 3 times a year. "Intruks for trafikkontroll" (Instruction for roadside inspection). Road Authorities. Continuously.
Poland	National Control Strategy. Ministry of Infrastructure. 2 years plan
Portugal	Euro Control Route. Instituto da Mobilidade e dos Transportes (IMT). Yearly plan.
Slovakia	Plan of main tasks and Content focus for the field of labour inspection. National Labour Inspectorate and The Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs and Family. Yearly plan.
Spain	Road Transport Inspection Plan. Ministerio de Transporte y Movilidad Sostenible. Yearly plan.
Sweden	Agreements on checks of commercial traffic on road. Swedish Transport Agency and Swedish Police Authority.
Switzerland	SKV (Ordinance on the Control of Road Transport). Federal Roads Office FEDRO

4.2 The roadside inspection.

Effective inspections necessitate adequate resources to ensure compliance with regulations. The integration of innovative technologies and the enhancement of existing inspection tools will significantly improve the quality and efficiency of enforcement activities. These advancements will provide enforcement authorities with more comprehensive insight into industry practices, enabling them to monitor compliance more effectively and address potential violations with greater precision.

4.2.1 Average time taken to complete an inspection.

A critical factor in the efficiency of roadside inspections is the average time required to complete them. This metric serves as a key performance indicator for evaluating the effectiveness of enforcement procedures and resource allocation. The duration of inspections can vary depending on several factors, including the complexity of the checks, the type of vehicle or operation being inspected, the level of technological integration in the inspection process, and the expertise and training of enforcement officers. Officers must ensure that vehicles comply with all applicable regulations, which, at a minimum, includes:

- Verifying authorized load weights and ensuring the type of load is permitted.
- Inspecting the vehicle for roadworthiness and identifying any mechanical defects.
- Reviewing tachograph records to assess compliance with driving and rest time regulations.
- Confirming the validity of the driver's vocational driving license.

Optimizing inspection efficiency provides several key advantages:

- **Minimizing disruption to logistics operations:** Reducing inspection times helps maintain transport efficiency, supporting the social and economic sustainability of logistics activities.
- **Maintaining traffic flow:** Streamlined inspections help prevent congestions and bottlenecks, thereby improving road safety and reducing the environmental impact of prolonged delays.
- **Targeting high-risk operators:** Faster and more effective inspections allow enforcement authorities to dedicate additional time and resources to high-risk vehicles and operators, enhancing overall enforcement efficiency.
- **Improving driver compliance and reducing stress:** Long inspections can be frustrating and stressful for drivers, particularly those operating under tight schedules. Efficient inspections foster cooperation and reduce resistance to compliance checks.
- **Promoting widespread compliance:** By increasing the number of vehicles inspected within a given timeframe, authorities enhance the likelihood of detecting non-compliance, deterring violations and raising overall sector-wide adherence to regulations.

These benefits highlight the importance of optimizing inspection processes to balance operational efficiency, regulatory compliance, and the well-being of all stakeholders in the road transport sector. It is essential for Member States to continuously assess and refine their inspection methodologies, ensuring that they strike

an appropriate balance between thorough scrutiny and operational efficiency. This ongoing improvement process is fundamental to facilitating the smooth flow of goods and services across the Single Market.

Enforcement authorities have been surveyed on the average duration of roadside inspections. Table 7 provides a summary of the responses from each country.

Table 7. Average time taken to complete a roadside inspection.

Country	Average time taken to complete a roadside inspection	Country	Average time taken to complete a roadside inspection
Austria	30 - 45 minutes	Lithuania	45 minutes
Belgium	20 minutes	Luxembourg	5-10 minutes to 30- 60 minutes
Bulgaria	5 –30 minutes	Netherlands	5 –45 minutes
Croatia	30 minutes minimum	Norway	15 (only documents) -45 minutes
Denmark	20 min to 2 hours. Usually, approx. 60 min (longer if there are found infringements)	Poland	45 minutes
Estonia	30 minutes	Portugal	30 minutes to 6 hours
Finland	40 minutes	Slovakia	The average time is not determined, but the total time (4 hours) for road inspection in one day is determined
Greece	30 minutes	Spain	20 minutes
Hungary	20-30 minutes	Sweden	15 minutes to 6 hours
Ireland	20 minutes	Switzerland	40 minutes
Latvia	30 minutes		

The responses indicate a high degree of consistency across all participating countries, with a minimum of 30 minutes typically required to conduct a thorough verification of all necessary documentation.

However, as previously mentioned, the total duration of a roadside inspection can vary significantly depending on several factors, including the complexity of the case, the number of detected infringements, the availability of technology, network coverage, and the number of enforcement officers involved. In a standard roadside inspection involving two enforcement officers—one reviewing tachograph data and the other verifying additional documentation—the process can generally be completed within approximately 20 minutes, provided that the driver has all required documents readily available.

In cases where documentation is missing, enforcement officers may grant the driver a specific time allowance to present the required documents. Under such circumstances, the inspection can extend to six hours or more, depending on the timeframe permitted by the officers.

This variability underscores the importance of ensuring that drivers carry all necessary documentation in a format that is easily verifiable and accessible, thereby facilitating efficient inspections and minimizing delays. To address this challenge, continued investment in advanced technologies and optimized procedures is essential to streamline the inspection process while maintaining its effectiveness.

4.2.2 Main technical & telematic means used.

The technical and telematic tools available to enforcement authorities play a crucial role in enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of roadside inspections. The adoption of advanced technologies such as Automatic Number Plate Recognition (ANPR), digital tachographs, Electronic Freight Transport Information (eFTI), and mobile enforcement units enables authorities to conduct compliance checks more rapidly, accurately, and efficiently. For instance, ANPR systems facilitate the instant capture and verification of vehicle registration data, allowing for the immediate detection of potential violations and enabling officers to respond swiftly.

When properly implemented and managed, these digital solutions not only reduce the workload of enforcement officers and minimize human error but also streamline enforcement operations and improve data accuracy. This, in turn, leads to higher compliance rates, enhanced road safety, and a fairer enforcement environment.

However, the effectiveness of these technical tools depends on their reliability, robustness, and interoperability across different enforcement systems. Seamless integration between national and EU platforms is essential for efficient data exchange among authorities. Achieving this requires harmonized standards, enhanced coordination, and sustained investment in system maintenance and technological upgrades.

Responses to the "Controlling Authority Opinion Survey" confirmed the widespread use of digital tools for roadside inspections and compliance checks. All participating entities reported using devices capable of downloading, analysing, and transmitting data from vehicle units or digital tachograph driver cards to central databases for further assessment. Additionally, all respondents confirmed having equipment to verify tachograph charts, while a majority (81%) reported using remote enforcement tools such as Dedicated Short-Range Communication (DSRC) or Remote Early Detection of Non-Compliance Risks (REDCR) systems.

Furthermore, almost all respondents (67%) indicated reliance on the Internal Market Information System (IMI), a platform designed to facilitate cross-border enforcement of driver posting rules and combat the presence of shell companies.

Table 8 provides a summary of the responses and an overview of the current technological landscape for road transport enforcement across the EU. The findings highlight the growing dependence on digital enforcement tools to enhance compliance monitoring, strengthen cross-border cooperation, and create a more transparent and efficient enforcement system

Table 8. Technical & telematic means to complete a roadside inspection

Country	Which are the main technical & telematic means you currently use for carrying out the controls and compliance checks?					
	Equipment capable of downloading data:	Remote interrogation equipment (DSRC/REDCR)	Information system for the single market (IMI)	On Board Units (OBU)	Digital platforms	Other
Austria	Control software solution from TachoEasy and VDO Download key	Yes		Yes		
Belgium	OCTET & TACHOSCAN with download keys from VDO and OCTET	Yes	Yes			
Bulgaria	A digital tachograph and driver card data analysis software (INELO, car tracker digital) and Software keys for downloading data from digital tachographs. A card reader is used, and the information is transferred to a laptop computer where the data is analysed using specialised software.	Yes	Yes		System for Road and Road Haulage Undertakings Inspections – only for BG drivers and vehicles, TACHONET	
Croatia	Download key, DSRC equipment, ADF Scanner; TachoSpeed Expert	Yes	Yes		Croatian Road Inspection System (CRIS)	
Denmark	Equipment capable of downloading data from both the vehicle unit and the driver card of the digital tachograph, reading and analysing the downloaded data, transmitting findings to a central database for further analysis, and verifying tachograph sheets when necessary.	Yes	Yes		Yes	Yes
Estonia	Equipment capable of downloading data from both the vehicle unit and the driver card of the digital tachograph, reading and analysing the downloaded data, transmitting findings to a central database for further analysis, and verifying tachograph sheets when necessary.	Yes	Yes		Yes	
Finland	TachoScan	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Greece	Equipment capable of downloading data from both the vehicle unit and the driver card of the digital tachograph, reading and analysing the downloaded data, transmitting findings to a central database for further analysis, and verifying tachograph sheets when necessary.					
Hungary	Chart analyser to check the tachograph sheet. Download key: the data are analysed by a driving and resting time software. The downloaded data are not collected to a database		Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Country	Which are the main technical & telematic means you currently use for carrying out the controls and compliance checks?					
	Equipment capable of downloading data:	Remote interrogation equipment (DSRC/REDCR)	Information system for the single market (IMI)	On Board Units (OBU)	Digital platforms	Other
Ireland	Chart readers for vehicles equipped with analogue tachographs, as well as card readers, download keys, and software for vehicles equipped with digital tachographs: DIS Transics, INELO download keys, and OCTET software. Additionally, all enforcement officers are equipped with control cards.	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Latvia	TchoScan, INELO	Yes	Yes		Yes	
Lithuania	Tachoreader device and the PC with Tachoscan software		Yes		Yes	
Luxembourg	Tachydrive NX, Tachodrive 5, Tachoscan Control by INELO.pl, Magnifying Glas, Scanner, Tachoreader (Basic) by INELO.pl	Yes	Yes			
Netherlands	Equipment capable of downloading data from both the vehicle unit and the driver card of the digital tachograph, reading and analysing the downloaded data, transmitting findings to a central database for further analysis, and verifying tachograph sheets when necessary.	Yes				
Norway	Equipment capable of downloading data from the driver card of the digital tachograph, reading and analysing the downloaded data, transmitting findings to a central database for further analysis, and verifying tachograph sheets when necessary.	Yes			Yes, proprietary intelligence systems and declaration systems	
Poland	Equipment capable of downloading data from both the vehicle unit and the driver card of the digital tachograph, reading and analysing the downloaded data, transmitting findings to a central database for further analysis, and verifying tachograph sheets when necessary.	Yes				
Portugal	TacoDrive5, TACHOSCAN CONTROL, DLK PRO DOWNLOAD KEYS					
Slovakia	Equipment capable of downloading data from both the vehicle unit and the driver card of the digital tachograph, reading and analysing the downloaded data, transmitting findings to a central database for further analysis, and verifying tachograph sheets when necessary.	Yes	Yes		Yes	

Country	Which are the main technical & telematic means you currently use for carrying out the controls and compliance checks?					
	Equipment capable of downloading data:	Remote interrogation equipment (DSRC/REDCR)	Information system for the single market (IMI)	On Board Units (OBU)	Digital platforms	Other
Spain	“TRAMO TRANSPORTE control system (tablet) in joint with a key from VDO “DLK PRO DOWNLOAD KEYS”	Yes	Yes		Yes	
Sweden	TachoSpeed	Yes	Yes		Yes	
Switzerland	Control at the heavy vehicle control centres (currently 10 centres) involves the use of inspection pits with control devices, brake test stands, diagnostic devices, weighing scales, electronic vehicle measurement, ARV/AETR software, and national register query applications (driver/owner). Mobile road control operations utilise diagnostic devices, mobile weighing scales, ARV/AETR software, and national register query applications (driver/owner).	Yes			National register query application (operator/owner)	

4.3 The roadside inspection and the digital platforms

The effectiveness of roadside inspections depends largely on the tools and processes employed, as enforcement authorities must balance thoroughness with efficiency to minimize disruptions for drivers and transport operators. Advances in digital technologies have significantly streamlined enforcement procedures, reducing inspection times. Platforms such as TACHOnet, ERRU (European Register of Road Transport Undertakings), and eFTI (Electronic Freight Transport Information) play an increasingly vital role in enhancing the efficiency and accuracy of roadside inspections. These systems enable authorities to quickly verify compliance, detect violations, and prevent redundant checks on already compliant vehicles, ultimately leading to more targeted and effective inspections.

Despite these advantages, integrating digital platforms into roadside inspections presents several challenges. Currently, most platforms operate independently, requiring enforcement officers to access multiple systems to obtain a comprehensive compliance overview. This lack of interoperability can slow down inspections and reduce overall effectiveness.

Moreover, utilizing these platforms necessitates substantial investment in both technology and training. Enforcement officers must be equipped with appropriate hardware—such as computers, tablets, or smartphones—and receive specialized training to ensure proficient use of digital tools. This training places considerable demands on the resources of enforcement authorities. For instance, in Spain, officers responsible for roadside inspections must complete a six-week specialized training program, combining theoretical and practical components in a hybrid in-person and online format. Additionally, they are required to attend refresher courses at least every three years to stay up to date with evolving digital enforcement tools.

When surveyed about the main digital platforms used for data exchange, more than half of enforcement authorities reported using TACHOnet (71%), IMI (67% of respondents), EUCARIS (57%), and ERRU (57%). However, only one respondent reported using eFTI platforms, highlighting the limited adoption of this framework among Europe.

Table 9 provides a summary of the responses from each country regarding the utilization of digital platforms for data sharing and retrieval.

Table 9. Main digital platforms use to complete a roadside inspection by country.

Main digital platforms use by country								
Country	eFTI platforms	ERRU	EUCARIS	IMI	RESPER	TACHOnet	TRACES	Other (Local digital platform)
Albania		applying for membership			applying for membership	applying for membership		
Austria			x			x	x	
Belgium			x	x				
Bulgaria		x	x	x	x	x		
Croatia				x		x		
Denmark		x	x	x	x	x	x	Digital platforms provided by the Danish Road Traffic Authority (Check transport undertaker data and risk classification)

Main digital platforms use by country								
Country	eFTI platforms	ERRU	EUCARIS	IMI	RESPER	TACHOnet	TRACES	Other (Local digital platform)
Estonia		x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Finland	x	x	x	x	x	x		
Greece								Pol (digital application of Hellenic Police), GSIS (General Secretariat for Information Systems)
Hungary			x	x		x		
Ireland		x	x	x	x	x		
Latvia		x		x				x
Lithuania		x		x		x		
Luxembourg				x		x	x	
Netherlands		x	x		x	x		
Norway		x	x		x	x	x	AutoSys, The Norwegian National Collection Agency, the Norwegian Labour Inspection Authority
Poland		x				x		
Portugal			x					PSP digital platform (Sistema Estratégico de Informação, Gestão e Controlo Operacional)
Slovakia				x		x		
Spain		x	x	x		x		Tramo Transporte
Sweden		x		x	x			
Switzerland								Only national platforms

Direct access to digital platforms is crucial for enforcement authorities, as it significantly enhances the accuracy and consistency of their operations while improving road safety in a timely and efficient manner. By accessing harmonized and up-to-date data, authorities can avoid errors or discrepancies that may arise from relying on outdated or fragmented information. This not only reduces inspection times and minimizes delays for compliant operators but also ensures that enforcement efforts are focused on high-risk vehicles and operators.

Furthermore, direct access to these platforms facilitates cross-border cooperation and information exchange, which is increasingly critical in the context of international road transport. By preventing non-compliant operators from exploiting regulatory gaps between countries, seamless data access strengthens the overall effectiveness of enforcement efforts.

Enforcement authorities were surveyed regarding their access to digital platforms for road transport compliance checks. Answers revealed that not all entities or officers within a given country have full access to all available platforms or the data stored within them. Permissions for accessing and consulting these platforms vary depending on each authority's specific enforcement responsibilities.

In almost all cases, roadside enforcement officers reported having direct access to these platforms through dedicated electronic applications, using credentials provided by their respective IT departments. However, when multiple platforms are used, respondents consistently highlighted the fragmented nature of access, as each system requires a separate registration process with distinct usernames and passwords.

Notably, only one-third of the surveyed authorities indicated that they could access all relevant platforms through a single access point, underscoring a significant lack of interoperability between existing enforcement tools.

Table 10 provides an overview of the methods used by each surveyed country to connect to these platforms and indicates whether enforcement authorities have direct access to them.

Table 10. Platforms connections by country.

Country	How do you connect to the platform?				
	Do you have direct access to it?	How do you connect to the platform?	In the event you use different digital platforms,		
			Is the process to connect to them the same?	Each one has its own registry (user name and password)?	Can you connect them through a single-entry point?
Austria	YES, I can directly access the platform	Via an electronic application, using credentials provided by my IT department	YES	YES	YES
Belgium	YES, I can directly access the platform	Via an electronic application, using credentials provided by my IT department	NO	YES	NO
Bulgaria	YES, direct access to RESPER and TACHOnet is available. For EUCARIS access, traffic police officers submit inquiries to the national contact point in accordance with Directive 2006/126/EC. Staff at the national contact point within the General Directorate of National Police conduct direct checks. Each authorised employee logging into the platform using their individual profile.	With TACHOnet connection via System for Road and Road Haulage Undertakings Inspections.	YES	YES	YES
Croatia	YES, I can directly access the platform	Via an electronic application, using credentials provided by my IT department	YES	YES	YES
Denmark	YES, I can directly access the platform	Depending on the case, the connection is via an electronic application using credentials provided by my IT department, or the connection is established by another colleague/department, or through other means such as EU-login or National electronic ID.	NO	YES	NO
Estonia	YES, I can directly access the platform	Depending on the case, the connection is via an electronic application using credentials provided by my IT department, or it is established by another colleague/department.	According to entity&position: YES/NO	According to entity&position: YES/NO	According to entity&position: YES/NO
Finland	YES, I can directly access the platform	Connection to it is established by another colleague/department.	---	YES	---

Country	How do you connect to the platform?				
	Do you have direct access to it?	How do you connect to the platform?	In the event you use different digital platforms,		
			Is the process to connect to them the same?	Each one has its own registry (user name and password)?	Can you connect them through a single-entry point?
Greece	Depending on the entity and position, I can directly access the platform, or I need to submit a request to another colleague or department with access to the platform.	Depending on the case, the connection is via an electronic application using credentials provided by my IT department, or it is established by another colleague or department.	NO	NO	NO
Hungary	Depending on the entity and position, I can directly access the platform, or I need to submit a request to another colleague or department with access to the platform.	Depending on the case, the connection is via an electronic application using credentials provided by my IT department, or it is established by another colleague or department.	According to entity&position: YES/NO	According to entity&position: YES/NO	According to entity&position: YES/NO
Ireland	YES, I can directly access the platform	Via an electronic application, by using credentials provided by my IT department	YES	---	YES
Latvia	NO, I need to make a request to another colleague/department who has access to the platform. IMI	Via an electronic application, by using credentials provided by my IT department	NO	YES	NO
Lithuania	YES, I can directly access the platform	Via an electronic application, by using credentials provided by my IT department	NO	YES	NO
Luxembourg	YES, I can directly access the platform	Via an electronic application, by using credentials provided by my IT department	NO	YES	NO
Netherlands	No, I need to submit a request to another colleague or department with access to the platform. The results of roadside inspections are submitted digitally to the National Contact Point (NCP) for ERRU/RSI (RDW in the Netherlands) via a national route and recorded in the national database (TVR). International exchanges via EUCARIS/RSI are conducted automatically at the NCP, which also receives RSI notifications from abroad regarding Dutch vehicles. There is	Via an electronic application, by using credentials provided by my IT department	---	---	---

Country	How do you connect to the platform?				
	Do you have direct access to it?	How do you connect to the platform?	In the event you use different digital platforms,		
			Is the process to connect to them the same?	Each one has its own registry (user name and password)?	Can you connect them through a single-entry point?
	a manual assessment procedure that outlining the steps to take.				
Norway	Depending on the entity and position, I can directly access the platform, or I need to submit a request to another colleague or department with access to the platform.	Depending on the case, the connection is via an electronic application using credentials provided by my IT department, or it is established by another colleague or department.	YES	NO	YES
Poland	YES, I can directly access the platform	Via an electronic application, by using credentials provided by my IT department	YES	---	---
Portugal	Depending on the entity and position, I can directly access the platform, or I need to submit a request to another colleague or department with access to the platform.	Depending on the case, the connection is via an electronic application using credentials provided by my IT department, or it is established by another colleague or department.	NO	NO	NO
Slovakia	YES, I can directly access the platform	Via an electronic application, by using credentials provided by my IT department	NO	YES	NO
Spain	YES, I can directly access the platform	Via an electronic application, by using credentials provided by my IT department	NO	YES (IMI)	YES (REST)
Sweden	NO, I need to make a request to another colleague/department who has access to the platform.	Via an electronic application, by using credentials provided by my IT department	---	---	---
Switzerland	YES, I can directly access the platform -Only national platforms	Via an electronic application, by using credentials provided by my IT department	---	---	---

Nearly all respondents (71%) agreed that digital platform queries typically generate real-time responses. However, regarding the use of the IMI system, some respondents noted that inquiries must be directed to the country of establishment, while others reported that responses could take up to 10 days. Additionally, several respondents highlighted that response times may vary depending on system availability, the operator, and actual network coverage—factors that should always be considered.

Table 11. Response Times of Digital Platforms by country

Country	Response Times of Digital Platforms
Austria	It works in real-time
Belgium	It works in real-time. IMI demand should be sent to the country of establishment
Bulgaria	It works in real-time
Croatia	It works in real-time
Denmark	It works in real-time
Estonia	It works in real-time
Finland	It works in real-time
Greece	It works in real-time
Hungary	It works in real-time
Ireland	It works in real-time
Latvia	IMI it is approximately 10 days
Lithuania	It works in real-time
Luxembourg	The response times are not consistent, it's not possible to determine a precise response time. Some work in real-time, others take a bit longer.
Netherlands	Some work in real-time, others depend on the platform, it can take some more time
Norway	It depends on availability and actual radio coverage but usually they work in real time
Poland	It works in real-time
Portugal	The response times are not consistent. Some works in real-time, others depend on the operator, but never at inspection time
Slovakia	It works in real-time
Spain	It works in real-time
Sweden	Other (unspecify)
Switzerland	It works in real-time

More than half of respondents (67%) recognized electronic applications and platforms as valuable tools for conducting enforcement checks on both national and foreign transport operators. They also indicated that they utilize the same application or platform for monitoring both categories of operators, ensuring consistency and efficiency in compliance verification. Table 12 summarizes the responses to this question by country.

Table 12. Digital Platforms for both domestic and non-domestic transport operators by country

Are these electronic applications/platforms helpful for conducting checks for both domestic and non-domestic transport operators?	
Yes, we use the same electronic application/platform for both	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Austria • Belgium • Bulgaria uses TACHOnet - data on the validity of driver cards for digital tachographs • Croatia. CRIS has connection with TACHOnet, and link is working • Estonia • Ireland uses a bespoke application developed for our enforcement purposes and it is used for recording roadside and premises inspections, PTI tests, and sanctions. It is linked to the Tachonet system and will soon be connected to the ERRU system once the EU Common Risk Rating Formula and ERRU 3 are implemented. • Lithuania employs the LTSA Information System for roadside checks, VEKTRA, which connects to TACHONET for card validity information and ERRU for licence validity checks, allowing direct information retrieval through VEKTRA. • Luxembourg (varies by entity) • Netherlands: utilises Eucaris for VIN checks and Kiwa for transport permits, while employing ERRU for non-domestic operator and community licence information, RESPER for driving licence verification, and TACHOnet for driver card checks, all implemented through the EUCARIS system. • Norway (depends on the entity, with some not using any electronic application or platform) • Poland • Portugal (varies by entity): PSP digital platform (Sistema Estratégico de Informação, Gestão e Controlo Operacional) is using for recording and controlling administrative offences related to goods transport inspections. This electronic platform lacks access to RESPER, TACHONET or ERRU. • Slovakia • Spain uses community licences, DTCO driver cards, and driver qualification cards.
No, we use different electronic applications/platforms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Denmark: ERRU is connected to digital platforms provided by the Danish Road Traffic Authority, while RESPER and TACHOnet are accessed on separate platforms from the same authority, with no single point of entry. • Finland • Hungary uses a domestic vehicle database, where inspectors fill out forms during roadside checks to generate reports, with data sent to a central database. • Latvia • Luxembourg varies by entity and includes CMR, tachograph records, and remuneration-related documents. • Sweden
We do not use any electronic application/platform	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Greece • Switzerland exclusively employs national platforms for its enforcement activities.

As key users of data-sharing platforms, enforcement authorities were surveyed on the main challenges and barriers that hinder the effectiveness and widespread adoption of these systems. All respondents agreed that significant challenges limit the efficiency and broader use of existing data-sharing platforms.

One of the primary challenges is the lack of awareness and insufficient training among road users and enforcement officers regarding the benefits and functionalities of these platforms. Many stakeholders remain unfamiliar with the potential advantages of digital enforcement tools, limiting their engagement and reducing

overall system efficiency. Additionally, the existence of multiple independent platforms—each requiring separate access credentials—places a considerable administrative burden on enforcement officers and transport operators. The absence of a unified system leads to inefficiencies, forcing users to conduct multiple searches across various databases, complicating enforcement procedures. Greater efforts are needed to educate and train all relevant parties on how these systems can enhance enforcement and facilitate compliance.

Another significant challenge is the inconsistency in how different Member States enter and utilize data within these systems. The lack of interoperability between platforms such as IMI, EUCARIS, RESPER, and TACHOnet results in fragmented enforcement efforts. In some cases, direct verification of a Community Licence for foreign hauliers is impossible, requiring time-consuming inquiries through official channels. Authorities strongly advocate for a single-entry portal similar to Denmark's "Finder" system, which would enable simultaneous searches across multiple registers, streamlining both national and international enforcement.

The availability and accessibility of enforcement data vary significantly across Member States. While some countries maintain online registers and databases, others lack the digital infrastructure necessary to support real-time data exchange. Differences in data formats and structures make it difficult for authorities to interpret and compare information, often requiring additional clarifications that slow down enforcement procedures. Other concerns include data privacy and security, interoperability limitations, and resistance among some stakeholders to transitioning to digital solutions, highlighting the need for a broader shift in mindset. Strict regulatory requirements, including those under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), further complicate data-sharing efforts, while outdated infrastructure and high implementation costs disproportionately impact smaller businesses.

Legal and administrative challenges also contribute to the inefficiencies of these platforms. In some countries, such as Greece, police officers do not have real-time access to enforcement databases, limiting their ability to conduct immediate roadside checks. The lack of cross-border cooperation and harmonized procedures further weakens the effectiveness of data-sharing platforms, as each Member State follows distinct regulatory frameworks and enforcement methodologies. In cases where international cooperation does exist, the complexity of communication channels often obstructs seamless data exchange. Hungary, for instance, faces resource limitations in software development, making digital integration a slow and costly process.

From an operational perspective, enforcement officers are frequently unable to retrieve real-time data during roadside inspections, requiring them to submit official requests that may take days to process. The fragmentation of responsibilities among various enforcement entities adds another layer of complexity, as access to relevant databases is frequently restricted or requires authorization from different administrative bodies. The current system forces officers to navigate multiple platforms to access essential information on tachographs, driving and rest time rules, Community Licences, and the posting of drivers. The IMI system, in particular, has been criticized for its limited accessibility and user-friendliness, with some Member States even excluded from key modules, such as those related to the posting of workers.

Resistance to data sharing also stems from concerns over data protection, legal constraints, and a lack of trust in digital enforcement mechanisms. Some companies are reluctant to share commercially sensitive information with public authorities, fearing potential misuse or exposure to competitors. Moreover, complex and non-user-friendly systems discourage engagement, with many users preferring traditional enforcement methods over digital alternatives.

Ultimately, the primary obstacle to the widespread adoption of data-sharing platforms is the excessive fragmentation of enforcement systems and the absence of a unified digital infrastructure. The inefficiencies

resulting from multiple independent platforms, lack of interoperability, and regulatory inconsistencies significantly hinder effective enforcement. Authorities strongly advocate for the development of a single, integrated platform with controlled access tailored to each Member State's competencies and responsibilities. Such a system would consolidate all relevant enforcement databases, streamline roadside inspections, and facilitate real-time document verification.

Addressing these challenges is essential to enhancing cross-border enforcement, ensuring compliance, and improving road safety across the EU.

Table 13 summarizes the responses to this question by country.

Table 13. Main challenges or barriers that prevent existing data-sharing platforms from being truly effective and widely used. By country

Country	In your opinion, what are the main challenges or barriers that prevent existing data-sharing platforms from being truly effective and widely used?
Austria	---
Belgium	There is insufficient awareness and training among road users regarding the added value of these digital tools. Greater efforts are needed to educate and inform stakeholders about their benefits. Currently, too many separate platforms exist, each requiring different access credentials, creating a burden for enforcement officers and transport operators. All relevant systems should be consolidated into a single, unified platform, ensuring that all systems are interconnected.
Bulgaria	The need for additional inquiries in certain cases and the varying approaches adopted by countries for entering and utilising data from the system pose challenges. Additionally, inspectors face limitations in their ability to conduct direct checks through ERRU to verify the presence of valid Community licences held by foreign hauliers.
Croatia	---
Denmark	The platforms are not directly interconnected and do not share information through a unified entry point. Information must be retrieved individually from different registers through multiple searches. There are too many different systems, each demanding unique login credentials. Additionally, obtaining information from RESPER requires direct communication with the Danish Road Traffic Authority. A common authority portal, similar to the Danish police's 'Finder' system, which can search multiple national registers and databases simultaneously, would be preferable. There is a strong desire for a consolidated entry point that encompasses both national and international systems. Ideally, this would allow the Danish Police to use the national electronic identification system 'MitId'.
Estonia	Not all Member States provide complete or even partial data. While certain Member States have online registers and databases, many do not. Moreover, data is not always presented in a consistent manner, and additional explanations are sometimes required to interpret it. Challenges include data privacy and security concerns, user's authentication requirements; interoperability and technical infrastructure, data standardisation issues, regulatory differences between regions, as well as the need for willingness and a shift in mindset.
Finland	Legislation
Greece	Police officers in the field in Greece do not have real-time access to the platforms. The primary barrier preventing widespread use of these platforms is the limited cooperation between law enforcement authorities of different countries. Furthermore, in specific cases where international cooperation exists, if the communication channel between officers is challenging, they are unable to share data effectively.
Hungary	There is currently no direct mechanism for data exchange. Hungary has limited resources for software development, and the process is time-consuming. Variations in regulations between countries and regions present challenges for international data sharing. Additionally, strict data security requirements, such as those imposed by the GDPR, can further slowdown data processing and

Country	In your opinion, what are the main challenges or barriers that prevent existing data-sharing platforms from being truly effective and widely used?
	exchange. Outdated infrastructure in many cases results in high implementation costs, placing a disproportionate burden on smaller businesses. From a user perspective, a lack of trust in the system may also hinder participation, for example, firms may be hesitant to share information, particularly commercially sensitive data, directly with public authorities. Furthermore, the complexity of existing systems or their lack of user-friendliness may discourage users from engaging with them.
Ireland	There is a significant amount of work involved in gaining access to these platforms and making the information available to enforcement officers, and at the roadside officers do not have time to be accessing multiple platforms for obtaining the necessary information. A single platform would be preferable with access controlled to different modules on it depending on the competence of the Member State Authority wishing to connect to it. For example, access to information/system linked to tachographs, driving and rest time rules, community licensing, posting of drivers, driver CPC, etc.
Latvia	On the platforms available to us, it is not possible to obtain operational information during roadside checks. Instead, it is necessary to send a request through official channels to the Member State concerned and wait several days for a response.
Lithuania	The primary obstacle to widespread adoption of sharing platforms is the proliferation of disparate systems. It is quite challenging to effectively utilise multiple different sharing platforms simultaneously. Furthermore, the cost of transferring data to a new platform would be considerably high due to the extensive scope of the information involved.
Luxembourg	The main barrier is the fact that every agency in Europe has different procedures concerning roadside inspections. Additionally, access to the IMI platform could be made easier and more user-friendly.
Netherlands	Data must be requested from various systems to carry out an RSI, especially because we carry out the RSI with multiple authorities.
Norway	The main challenge is that Norway, being outside the EU, has only limited access to a few of these systems. Norwegian Customs primarily focuses on goods-carrying capacity and only secondarily engages with the transport domain. Digital platforms are used for all roadside inspections, and there are no significant barriers to sharing data.
Poland	---
Portugal	The main challenge is achieving interoperability between various IT platforms from different entities to extract the necessary information for enforcement, such as IMT, EUCARIS, and other European platforms like RESPER and TACHOnet. Additional obstacles include limited access to platforms, a lack of data-rich platforms, and constraints imposed by personal data protection regulations.
Slovakia	Long response times from authorities pose a significant challenge, exacerbating the complexity of posting cases. This issue is compounded by the low number of administrative staff in Member States handling the IMI system and noncompliance from service providers. Additionally, the exclusion of certain Member State authorities from specific modules of IMI, particularly in the posting of workers modules, further hinders effective information exchange and enforcement.
Spain	The primary challenge stems from the division of responsibilities in transport inspections. While police forces conduct transport inspections, they do so in support of the Ministry of Transport's transport inspection, which holds the legal jurisdiction as the official Administrative Body. Consequently, access to databases can only be obtained with authorization from the aforementioned official body, rather than through full access. An additional issue is that various access platforms are managed by different organizations, such as IMI. To address these challenges, a comprehensive single access point is required, utilizing a single username and password that would grant full access to all relevant databases.
Sweden	---
Switzerland	Data protection and lack of legal basis

Respondents were also asked to identify specific needs or use cases that are not adequately addressed by existing data exchange platforms. While some indicated that their current systems provide the necessary tools, the majority highlighted several critical gaps that hinder enforcement effectiveness and operational efficiency.

The most frequently cited need is real-time access to transport licenses across all EU countries, enabling enforcement officers to verify vehicle licensing based on registration plates. Similarly, access to databases containing transport company information was emphasized, as the current TACHOnet system does not allow for a comprehensive search of all issued driver cards.

Another significant shortcoming is the absence of a unified European database integrating all transport-related electronic registers. Such a system would streamline enforcement checks and improve efficiency. Respondents also stressed the need for a single platform that allows enforcement officers to verify the PTI status of any EU-registered vehicle, similar to the system currently available in Ireland for domestically registered vehicles. Additionally, access to border crossing data from all Member States, along with risk ratings of foreign companies, was identified as crucial for effective oversight and enforcement.

The ability to obtain comprehensive vehicle data for non-domestic vehicles remains a challenge, as this information is currently only available for countries connected to EUCARIS. Respondents also underscored the importance of enabling enforcement officers to conduct technical inspections on foreign-registered vehicles. Furthermore, there is a pressing need for an EU-wide system to facilitate the secure payment of security deposits for fines, ensuring reliability for both control authorities and operators. The establishment of a shared database for certificates of competence in animal transport and a unified European register of criminal sentences was also highlighted as necessary to enhance transparency and enforcement capabilities.

Another key requirement is a system that allows enforcement officers to check documents and submit results to transport companies without immediately closing the case. Current digital platforms do not fully support such functionalities, limiting the flexibility of enforcement procedures.

From a technical perspective, respondents identified several limitations in existing systems. One of the main concerns is the restricted data transfer capacity, as illustrated by the small file allowances in IMI requests, which permit only 20 MB for posting-related information and 5 MB for document requests in the road transport sector. Additionally, the IMI system's email notification mechanism was deemed inadequate, as it often fails to provide sufficient information about requests, leading to overlooked comments and updates. The inability to translate documents within the system further complicates enforcement procedures, creating additional administrative burdens.

A major challenge remains the fragmentation of access platforms, which are managed by multiple organizations. Respondents strongly advocated for the development of a unified access system with a single username and password that would provide full access to all enforcement databases. The lack of interoperability between different enforcement tools complicates roadside inspections and increases the administrative workload for enforcement officers.

Finally, direct access to EUCARIS was repeatedly highlighted as a critical requirement for improving enforcement capabilities. The current limitations on accessing vehicle and driver data from other Member States undermine the effectiveness of roadside checks and cross-border enforcement efforts. Addressing these challenges is essential for enhancing compliance monitoring, improving enforcement efficiency, and strengthening road safety across the EU.

Table 14 below provides a summary of the specific needs and use cases that are not adequately addressed by existing data-sharing platforms, as reported by each country.

Table 14. Digital Platforms—by country

Country	What specific user needs or use cases are not addressed by existing data-sharing platforms?
Austria	---
Belgium	The ability to view all transport licenses across all EU countries in real time would enable enforcement officers to verify whether a checked vehicle is properly licensed based on its registration plate.
Bulgaria	Having the capability to conduct technical inspections on vehicles with foreign registration.
Croatia	---
Denmark	An EU-wide solution for the payment of security deposits for fines should be established to ensure secure payment for both the control authority and the operator. Additionally, a common European database for certificates of competence in animal transport and a unified European register of criminal sentences are necessary to enhance transparency and enforcement.
Estonia	Access to border crossing data from all Member States, along with the risk ratings of foreign companies, is essential for effective enforcement and oversight.
Finland	---
Greece	Real-time awareness of the existing vehicle and cargo information.
Hungary	The access to databases containing information on transport companies. The current TACHOnet system does not allow for a comprehensive search of all issued cards related to a specific driver.
Ireland	A common platform where enforcers could input a vehicle registration number and receive the PTI status of the vehicle, indicating whether it is valid or not, would be highly beneficial. While such systems exist for nationally registered vehicles in Ireland, it would be advantageous to extend this access to include information for any EU-registered vehicle.
Latvia	A single European database integrating all transport-related electronic registers to be checked.
Lithuania	We currently have no comments. The systems we are using already provide the necessary tools.
Luxembourg	A system that allows enforcement officers to check documents and submit results to transport companies without immediately closing the case.
Netherlands	---
Norway	Currently, we do not have access to comprehensive vehicle data for non-domestic vehicles. This information is only available for countries that are connected to EUCARIS.
Poland	---
Portugal	While current systems allow for the registration of infractions, they lack comprehensive access to other crucial information. Access to the following data is necessary: Vehicle documentation, including licenses; Goods transportation documents, such as transport manifests; Driver documentation, including driver's licenses and professional certificates. There is a notable absence of data-sharing platforms specifically designed for consulting and entering information about goods transportation.
Slovakia	From a more technical perspective, we would like to highlight several issues: the limited data transfer capacity, exemplified by the small allowances in IMI requests (20 MB for information concerning posting and only 5 MB for document requests in the road transport sector); the inadequacy of the email notification system, which fails to provide sufficient information about IMI requests, often resulting in overlooked additional comments and notes made within the system; and the inability to translate documents provided within the system.
Spain	From the perspective of road control operations, the current digital infrastructure largely meets the needs of users, with one significant exception: the fragmentation of access platforms, managed by various organizations. There is a need for a unified access system through a single username and a single password that allow full access to all the databases.

Country	What specific user needs or use cases are not addressed by existing data-sharing platforms?
Sweden	---
Switzerland	Access to EUCARIS platforms

4.4 Roadside inspection and data verification

Roadside inspections are conducted to ensure that drivers, vehicles, and cargo comply with safety, environmental, and labour regulations, thereby reducing the risk of accidents and promoting fair competition. A key aspect of these inspections is data verification, which enables authorities to confirm the accuracy and authenticity of information provided by drivers and operators. Effective data verification minimizes errors and fraudulent activities, ensuring enforcement actions are based on credible evidence. This is essential for maintaining the integrity and effectiveness of the enforcement process.

Given the cross-border nature of road transport operations, cooperation among enforcement authorities across EU Member States is crucial. By integrating roadside inspections with robust data verification mechanisms, authorities can enhance road safety, protect the environment, and improve the efficiency of the EU's transport system. Commercial road transport—both passengers and goods—serves as the backbone of modern mobility and supply chains, playing a vital role in facilitating the safe and efficient movement of goods and people across Europe, and contributing to economic growth and social well-being. This sector is supported by approximately 4 million professional drivers, who are integral to the EU's logistics network. These drivers undergo comprehensive training and periodic retraining to uphold high safety standards (International Road Transport Union (IRU), 2022). Ensuring that only qualified and certified drivers operate within the sector is a fundamental responsibility of enforcement authorities.

The process of verifying driver documentation during roadside inspections across the EU is evolving, however, significant inconsistencies persist between Member States. Some countries, such as France and Spain, permit drivers to present digital versions of their licenses and certificates on mobile devices during inspections. In Spain, for instance, enforcement officers provide drivers with a QR code to submit their documentation digitally, which is then linked to the control file. This digital approach improves efficiency and reduces reliance on physical documents. Nevertheless, in many countries physical documents remain the primary means of verification. The lack of harmonized procedures across EU Member States creates inconsistencies in roadside checks and driver documentation verification, highlighting the need for a standardized and interoperable system across the EU. Verifying driving licenses and Certificates of Professional Competence (CPC) during roadside inspections is critical to ensuring road safety and regulatory compliance, as these documents confirm that drivers possess the necessary skills, knowledge, and qualifications to operate commercial vehicles safely.

Stakeholders were asked about their methods for verifying driving licenses and CPCs presented by drivers from other EU Member States. Their responses revealed significant variations in practices among enforcement authorities. A considerable proportion (62%) rely solely on information presented by drivers without conducting further verification. Others use established digital platforms such as the EU Driving License Network (RESPER) (29%) or the European Car and Driving License Information System (EUCARIS) for verification. In cases where doubts arise regarding the legitimacy of a license, some authorities conduct additional inquiries via email or telephone with the issuing institutions. Additional verification methods include consulting national registries, using dedicated enforcement databases (e.g., ProDrive for CPC verification), conducting visual inspections combined with driver interviews, or involving intelligence units through police cooperation centres or ministries of transport.

These findings underscore the inconsistencies in verification procedures across Member States. While some authorities utilize digital systems, others rely on direct consultations or trust-based assessments. Enhancing cooperation between Member States and integrating existing platforms into a single user-friendly system would facilitate faster and more reliable verification processes, ensuring that only qualified and legally authorized drivers operate on European roads.

Table 15 provides a summary of responses to this question by country.

Table 15. How do you verify the driving licenses and competence certificates (Driver CPC) presented by a driver who is not from your country?

Country	How do you verify the driving licenses and competence certificates (Driver CPC) presented by a driver who is not from your country?
Austria	Police cooperation centre
Belgium	I rely on the information presented by the driver without conducting further verification.
Bulgaria	I utilize the EU Driving License Network (RESPER) for verification purposes. Additionally, inquiries regarding driving licenses are occasionally made via email to the competent institutions. In some cases, I rely on the information provided by the driver without conducting further verification.
Croatia	I rely on the information presented by the driver without conducting further verification.
Denmark	I rely on the information provided by the driver without conducting further verification. Access to RESPER is not available during roadside checks. Verification requires contacting a national contact point.
Estonia	I utilize both the EU Driving License Network (RESPER) and the European Car and Driving License Information System (EUCARIS)
Finland	I utilize the EU Driving License Network (RESPER).
Greece	I rely on the information presented by the driver without conducting further verification.
Hungary	I contact the relevant authority in the country that issued the license or certificate, either by phone or email, to verify its authenticity. However, in some cases, I rely on the information provided by the driver without conducting further verification.
Ireland	I utilize the EU Driving License Network (RESPER) and the ProDrive system to verify the Certificates of Professional Competence (CPCs) of foreign drivers. For Irish drivers, all CPC information is readily accessible in our enforcement database.
Latvia	Visual inspection and driver enquiry
Lithuania	I rely on the information presented by the driver without conducting further verification.
Luxembourg	We verify the provided information against our national registry. In some instances, however, we rely on the information presented by the driver without conducting further verification.
Netherlands	I do not carry out this check (other organisation; Police)
Norway	I utilize the EU Driving License Network (RESPER). In cases where suspicion arises, our intelligence units conduct additional checks.
Poland	I rely on the information presented by the driver without conducting further verification.
Portugal	I rely on the information presented by the driver.
Slovakia	I do not carry out this check
Spain	By requesting information from the Ministry of Transport
Sweden	I contact the relevant authority in the country that issued the license or certificate, either by telephone or email, to verify its authenticity. On occasion, I rely solely on the information provided by the driver without conducting additional verification.

Country	How do you verify the driving licenses and competence certificates (Driver CPC) presented by a driver who is not from your country?
Switzerland	Verification of the authenticity of documents and, in suspicious cases, direct verification enquiries in the country of origin.

Technological advancements continue to provide innovative solutions that enhance safety and streamline daily operations. This ongoing progress has significantly influenced road transport technology, driven by the imperative to improve safety, efficiency, and compliance with EU regulations. A key development in this regard is the introduction of smart tachographs, which represent a major step forward in monitoring road transport operations and enhancing road safety. These advanced devices reduce the risk of tachograph manipulation through robust anti-tampering measures, including encrypted communication and advanced authentication mechanisms.

Figure 8. Timeline for the introduction of the second-generation smart tachograph. (European Commission, s.f.)

The new generation of tachographs, known as smart tachographs, offers substantial improvements over previous models by incorporating sophisticated features designed to enhance compliance monitoring and enforcement. All smart tachographs are equipped with:

- a Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) module, which records the vehicle's location at the beginning and end of each journey and updates its position every three hours. It also automatically logs border crossings, improving the monitoring of cabotage operations and driver movements.
- an Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS) interface, facilitating seamless data exchange with external systems, such as data download solutions and mobile applications.
- a Dedicated Short-Range Communication (DSRC) interface, which enables roadside inspectors to remotely access tachograph data via short-range radio devices, eliminating the need to stop the vehicle.

Table 16. Summary of the data send over DSRC interface described in Appendix 14, Implementing Regulation (EU) 2016/799. (European Commision, 2023)

List of data accessible to the controlling authority without stopping the vehicle:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – RTM1: Vehicle registration plate – RTM2: Speeding event – RTM3: Driving without valid card – RTM4: Valid driver card – RTM5: Card insertion while driving – RTM6: Motion data error – RTM7: Vehicle motion conflict – RTM8: Second driver card – RTM9: Current activity – RTM10: Last closed session – RTM11: Power supply interruption – RTM12: Sensor fault – RTM13: Time adjustment – RTM14: Security breach attempt – RTM15: Last calibration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – RTM16: Previous calibration RTM17: Date tachograph connected – RTM18: Current speed – RTM19: Timestamp – RTM20: Time at which the latest authenticated vehicle position was available – RTM21: Continuous driving time – RTM22: Longest daily driving time for the ongoing and previous RTM-shift, calculated in accordance with the Addendum to Appendix 14 – RTM23: Longest daily driving time within the ongoing week, calculated in accordance with the Addendum to Appendix 14 – RTM24: Weekly driving time, calculated in accordance with the Addendum in Appendix 14 – RTM25: Fortnightly driving time, calculated in accordance with the addendum in Appendix 14

Enforcement agencies can remotely access and interrogate these smart tachographs without requiring explicit permission from the vehicle operator. This capability allows regulatory bodies to discreetly monitor compliance and retrieve relevant data, enhancing their ability to enforce driving time regulations and other transport laws. The transmitted data only indicates whether any infringements or signs of tachograph manipulation have been detected. If no violations are identified, authorities can avoid unnecessary roadside checks, improving efficiency for both enforcement officers and drivers.

However, data obtained through remote monitoring does not automatically result in fines or sanctions for drivers or transport companies. Any detected irregularities necessitate stopping the vehicle for a thorough inspection before penalties can be imposed, ensuring fairness and accuracy in enforcement procedures.

Tachograph manipulation enables unscrupulous drivers and companies to exceed legal driving hours, posing serious risks to road safety and distorting fair competition within the transport sector. Given the crucial role of tachographs in ensuring compliance with EU regulations, enforcement authorities were surveyed on their methods for verifying the validity of a driver's tachograph card (Table 17).

A significant proportion of respondents (67%) reported using the TACHOnet platform for verification. Some authorities also conduct additional document authenticity checks and, in cases of suspicion, make direct inquiries with national road authorities, such as the Federal Roads Office.

However, some respondents indicated that they rely solely on visual inspections or information provided by drivers, without cross-referencing official databases. Others reported lacking access to digital verification systems, while some stated that they verify tachograph card validity only in specific intelligence-led or inspection cases, often in cooperation with other authorities. In certain instances, verification is carried out through phone calls or email exchanges with the issuing country's competent authority, a process that can delay enforcement actions.

These findings highlight the need to expand access to digital verification tools, particularly TACHOnet, for all enforcement authorities across the EU. Systematic and immediate verification of tachograph cards during roadside inspections is essential to detecting fraud, ensuring compliance, and upholding road safety

standards. Greater integration of verification systems and enhanced cross-border cooperation would further strengthen enforcement efforts, preventing violations and ensuring a level playing field in the transport sector.

Table 17. How do you verify the validity of a driver's tachograph card?

Country	How do you verify the validity of a driver's tachograph card?
Austria	I use the TACHONET platform
Belgium	I trust the information presented to me by the driver and do not make any verification because we still don't have access
Bulgaria	I use the TACHONET platform
Croatia	I use the TACHONET platform
Denmark	I use the TACHONET platform
Estonia	I use the TACHONET platform
Finland	I use the TACHONET platform
Greece	I trust the information presented to me by the driver and do not make any verification
Hungary	I use the TACHONET platform and sometimes I trust the information presented to me by the driver and do not make any verification
Ireland	I use the TACHONET platform. For Irish drivers the data is available in our enforcement database, access to which is provided to all our officers for conducting roadside and premises inspections
Latvia	Visual inspection and driver enquiry
Lithuania	I make a phone call or email the concerned authority in another country that issued the card
Luxembourg	I use the TACHONET platform and sometimes I trust the information presented to me by the driver and do not make any verification
Netherlands	I do not carry out this check (another organisation; ILT)
Norway	I use the TACHONET platform
Poland	I use the TACHONET platform
Portugal	I trust the information presented to me by the driver
Slovakia	I use the TACHONET platform
Spain	I use the TACHONET platform
Sweden	I make a phone call or email the concerned authority in another country that issued the card. Sometimes I trust the information presented to me by the driver and do not make any verification.
Switzerland	Verification of the authenticity of documents and, in suspicious cases, direct enquiry with the Federal Roads Office.

Only 43% of respondents reported having access to information on transport companies and managers from other countries (Table 18). The ability to verify such data is essential for ensuring compliance with EU transport regulations, preventing fraud, and maintaining fair competition within the sector. However, the responses indicate that access remains limited and varies significantly among enforcement authorities.

Among those with access, the most common method of verification is through national electronic registers via the European Road Transport Undertakings Register (ERRU) platform. While twelve countries participating in the survey reported having access to ERRU, only six indicated that they actively use it for these checks.

Some respondents rely on publicly available data under Article 16(2) of Regulation (EC) No 1071/2009, which grants access to basic company information. In other cases, authorities can only retrieve data on domestic

transport operators through national compliance databases, restricting their ability to verify foreign operators effectively. Notably, only one country reported using the Road Transport Posting Declaration system, which was introduced to ensure compliance with Directive (EU) 2020/1057 on the posting of drivers. This platform enables operators to submit posting declarations to the Member States where their drivers will be posted and to provide requested documentation to the relevant authorities when required.

For other enforcement officers, access to data is case-dependent, with some relying on intelligence units to obtain relevant information. The lack of direct and consistent access to company records from other Member States presents a significant challenge for effective road enforcement. Strengthening data exchange mechanisms, improving interoperability between national registries, and ensuring timely access to relevant company data would greatly enhance the efficiency of cross-border transport controls and regulatory compliance across the EU.

Table 18. Can you access information on Transport Companies/Managers from other countries?

Can you access information on Transport Companies/Managers from other countries?	
NO	YES (how you access to this information)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Austria • Belgium • Bulgaria • Croatia • Denmark - currently lacks access to verify transport undertaking data (CTUD) via ERRU. The National Road Traffic Authority is developing a national digital platform that will eventually provide this access. • Greece • Latvia • Lithuania • Luxembourg • Netherlands • Slovakia • Switzerland 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Estonia - consults the national electronic registers of other countries via ERRU platform. • Finland - consults the national electronic registers of other countries via ERRU platform. • Hungary - uses the publicly accessible data according to Article 16(2) of Regulation (EC) No 1071/2009 • Ireland - Currently, roadside access to company data is limited to Irish operators through our enforcement database or publicly available websites. Within the next 2-3 months, we anticipate implementing enhanced access to information on foreign operators at roadside checks, as mandated by the ERRU version 3 regulations. • Norway - employs a dual approach: consultation of national electronic registers of other countries via ERRU platform and requests through intelligence unit. • Poland - consults the national electronic registers of other countries via ERRU platform. • Portugal - We currently have access to the Road Transport Posting Declaration portal (https://www.postingdeclaration.eu/scan) • Spain - consults the national electronic registers of other countries via ERRU platform. • Sweden - Depends on the case

The verification of transport company information varies among enforcement authorities, depending on their operational procedures and the tools available to them. According to Table 19, the majority of respondents indicated that these checks are conducted during roadside inspections. This approach allows for immediate compliance verification and enables prompt enforcement action when necessary. Additionally, it facilitates direct interaction with drivers, enabling officers to clarify any discrepancies on the spot, potentially reducing the need for follow-up investigations or administrative procedures.

Some authorities extend their verification process beyond roadside checks by conducting additional inquiries before or after the inspection. This method allows for a more comprehensive review, particularly in cases where real-time access to information is limited or further investigation is required.

However, a portion of respondents reported that they do not conduct such verifications at all. This highlights potential gaps in enforcement capabilities and underscores the need for improved access to digital platforms and cross-border data-sharing mechanisms. Strengthening these processes would enhance the effectiveness of transport regulation enforcement and contribute to a more harmonized and efficient control system across the EU.

Table 19. In general, when do you verify this information?

Country	When do you verify this information?		
	Prior to a roadside check	During to a roadside check	After a roadside check
Austria		----	
Belgium		----	
Bulgaria	This check is not carried out		
Croatia		----	
Denmark	If something looks suspicious inquiries can be made to the Danish Road Traffic Authority		
Estonia	----	----	
Finland		----	
Greece			----
Hungary		----	----
	The information in the previous point will be examined in the follow-up procedure in the event of infringement		
Ireland		----	
Latvia		----	
Lithuania	This check is not carried out		
Luxembourg		----	----
Netherlands	This check is not carried out		
Norway	----	----	----
Poland		----	
Portugal		----	
Slovakia		----	
Spain		----	
Sweden	Depends on		
Switzerland		----	

When a violation is detected during data verification at a roadside inspection, enforcement authorities follow a structured process to ensure compliance, uphold road safety, and effectively enforce applicable regulations. Immediate documentation of the violation is essential to maintaining the integrity of the enforcement process, providing a clear and legally sound record of the infraction.

In cases involving foreign operators, drivers, or vehicles, enforcement authorities may escalate the matter through cross-border cooperation mechanisms. This ensures that non-compliant operators cannot evade enforcement simply by crossing borders, thereby promoting fairness and ensuring the uniform application of transport regulations across the EU. Effective cooperation between Member States strengthens enforcement efforts and prevents regulatory loopholes that could undermine road safety and fair competition.

Once enforcement actions are taken, authorities formally notify the driver and/or operator of the infringement. This notification includes a detailed description of the violation, the circumstances under which it occurred, and the associated penalties.

In this context, respondents were asked how they document and process infringements (Table 20). Almost half (48%) of the respondents reported using a combination of paper and digital forms, while 24% rely exclusively on paper documentation. However, an increasing number of enforcement agencies have transitioned to fully digital systems, utilizing telematic platforms such as TRAMO TRANSPORTE and VStV to enhance efficiency and streamline data processing. Additionally, some authorities are planning to fully digitize roadside inspection records in the near future.

These findings highlight the ongoing modernization of enforcement procedures within the EU, with a clear trend toward digital solutions aimed at improving efficiency, accuracy, and cross-border enforcement capabilities.

Table 20. Means used to report an infringement.

If you detect an infraction during the control, you will file the infringement using.		
Paper forms	Telematics data	Combination
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Belgium • Croatia • Luxembourg • Slovakia • Switzerland 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Austria - VStV and national ERRU (VUR) • Lithuania - Telematics data: We have information system "VEKTRA" • Netherlands: RDW based data store (TVR). • Norway: Proprietary systems • Poland • Spain: TRAMO TRANSPORTE control system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bulgaria • Denmark – ERRU, Tachoscan and Danish national police IT program: POLSAS. • Estonia • Finland • Greece • Hungary - During roadside checks, the inspector completes a digital form, which is subsequently printed on paper. The collected data are then transmitted to a central database. • Ireland - Currently, our inspection records are documented on paper during roadside checks and manually entered into our database within 5 days of the inspection. However, we are transitioning to electronic inspection data capture at the roadside, which is scheduled to be implemented in 2025. • Latvia • Portugal – PSP digital platforms (Sistema Estratégico de Informação, Gestão e Controlo Operacional) • Sweden

One of the key aspects of roadside inspections in road transport controls is efficient time management. While these checks are essential for ensuring road safety and regulatory compliance, they can also create inefficiencies and increase stress for drivers. Inspections should be completed as swiftly as possible while remaining legally sound and practically manageable, minimizing delays and disruptions to transport operations.

Respondents were asked to identify the main challenges they face during roadside inspections (Table 21). The vast majority reported similar difficulties, with 81% highlighting delays caused by waiting for drivers to provide essential documents. The challenge of verifying the authenticity of documents across Member States remains a significant concern, as reported by more than half of respondents. Specifically, 76% indicated that enforcement officers are often required to review paper-based documentation, which requires manual data entry into multiple systems—an inefficient process prone to errors. Additionally, 71% of respondents noted the need to access several separate systems to obtain all necessary information, further complicating and prolonging the inspection process.

Almost half (48%) of the respondents cited the inability to inspect trucks without stopping them as a significant limitation, reducing the efficiency of enforcement efforts. In some cases, intelligence-based checks are used, relying on proprietary systems to improve targeting.

Additionally, almost a quarter of respondents (19%) identified the lack of real-time data on truck flows as a key challenge in establishing effective checkpoints.

Other reported difficulties include language barriers, where drivers either cannot or claim they cannot communicate in English or provide documentation in English. Furthermore, collecting evidence when a violation is detected can be time-consuming, particularly when requiring a deposit for fine payments. Some enforcement authorities also lack the ability to verify document authenticity across Member States, further complicating enforcement efforts. In certain jurisdictions, officers are only permitted to inspect vehicles that have already been stopped, their ability to conduct proactive enforcement.

Table 21. Main challenges during control inspections

What are your main challenges during the control inspection?						
Country	Paper documents that consume lot of time for checking because the data must be inserted manually in the different systems	Needs to connect lot of different systems to check all information	Needs to wait for driver to provide all necessary information	No possibility of checking truck without stopping them	No data available about flow of truck on the road to setup the check points	Other
Austria	Yes	Yes	Yes			
Belgium		Yes				
Bulgaria			Yes			
Croatia	Yes			Yes		
Denmark	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes		If a violation is found, it can be time-consuming to collect evidence and if necessary, a deposit for the payment of a fine
Estonia	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Finland		Yes	Yes			
Greece	Yes		Yes	Yes	Yes	
Hungary	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Ireland	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Drivers who cannot (or claim they cannot) speak English or provide support documentation in English
Latvia	Yes	Yes	Yes			It is not possible to verify the authenticity of the document to other Member States
Lithuania	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes		

What are your main challenges during the control inspection?						
Country	Paper documents that consume lot of time for checking because the data must be inserted manually in the different systems	Needs to connect lot of different systems to check all information	Needs to wait for driver to provide all necessary information	No possibility of checking truck without stopping them	No data available about flow of truck on the road to setup the check points	Other
Luxembourg			Yes			We're not allowed to stop the drivers; we just check stopped trucks.
Netherlands	Yes	Yes	Yes			
Norway		Yes	Yes			Checks of intelligence is often used, from proprietary systems
Poland	Yes					
Portugal	Yes		Yes	Yes		
Slovakia	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes		
Spain	Yes	Yes	Yes			
Sweden	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes		Yes
Switzerland	Yes	Yes				

4.5 Roadside Inspections: Improvements suggest by enforcement authorities

KEYSTONE is developing a standardized Application Programming Interface (API) to facilitate the seamless exchange of critical transport data between logistics operators and enforcement authorities. The objective is to establish KEYSTONE as a practical tool for competent authorities, enhancing the efficient roadside inspections. By optimizing the verification process, this initiative aims to improve road safety, regulatory compliance, and operational efficiency across the EU transport system.

To determine the most relevant data for enforcement authorities in the context of road transport controls, respondents were asked to identify the specific information they would find most useful. Their responses highlighted several key data points essential for effective enforcement, including real-time, integrated access to vehicle, driver, cargo, and company data. Respondents emphasized the need for standardized, cross-border data sharing while ensuring full compliance with legal and security requirements.

One of the primary concerns is access to loading and unloading points, as well as comprehensive cargo documentation, including CMRs, waybills, and manifests. Information about cargo type, particularly hazardous goods (ADR), is crucial, along with details on transport permits, border crossings, and Automatic Number Plate Recognition (ANPR) data. Authorities also highlighted the need for tracking goods down to the individual pallet level and monitoring the movements of semi-trailers and towing units within an operator's fleet to strengthen enforcement of cabotage and posting regulations.

Enforcement officers require detailed driver-related information, including driving licenses, employment contracts, professional certifications, tachograph data, and records of previous infractions. Additionally,

access to evidence of transport operations -such as tachograph records, timesheets, payslips, and proof of payment- is essential for verifying compliance with labour and social regulations.

For vehicle-related data, respondents emphasized the need to match vehicle plate and chassis numbers in real-time with owner identification and link them to prior traffic offenses and insurance details. They also stressed the importance of accessing Periodic Technical Inspection (PTI) records, tolling data, and ferry manifests to monitor vehicle movements across borders.

In terms of company-related information, authorities highlighted the need for electronic contact details of transport managers, records of third-country transport operations, and a comprehensive compliance history, including past infractions and any discrepancies.

Finally, respondents emphasized that data sharing must be legally regulated to ensure secure and lawful exchanges between enforcement authorities across Member States. A centralized platform integrating all relevant transport data would significantly enhance enforcement efficiency and cross-border cooperation.

Table 22 provides a summary of responses from each country.

Table 22. The most relevant data for enforcement authorities by country

Country	KEYSTONE is defining standard API for allowing logistic operators to share their data with authorities. What data are you more interested in?
Austria	Loading and unloading points
Belgium	CMR's, licences and data of tachograph from other trucks
Bulgaria	Driver data, driver's document data, and data for the route of the goods - as shown on the CMR.
Croatia	---
Denmark	To enhance the monitoring of cabotage and posting regulations, enforcement authorities require access to information regarding the movements of semi-trailers and towing units within an operator's fleet management system. Additionally, the capability to track goods right down to individual pallets.
Estonia	Cargo documents, border crossing information, ANPR data, driver employment contracts or registration details, transport manager names, and the number of certified true copies. More data leads to better enforcement outcomes. Data sharing must be conducted strictly within the confines of existing laws, and regulations are necessary.
Finland	---
Greece	CMR and type of the cargo (ADR, etc.) Vehicle plate Number / chassis number be matched with owner's ID: Vehicle plate number be matched with all its traffic offenses Vehicle owner's ID be matched with all his traffic offenses Vehicle plate number be matched with its cargo in real time
Hungary	Companies electronic contact details, third country transport operations and cabotage operations. Data relevant to the transport of dangerous goods: data on the vehicle and its combination, data on the driver (driving licence, validity and scope of ADR 8.2 driving licence), data on the dangerous goods consigned, transport documents (bilateral/multilateral agreements, permits, data on the transport undertaking, place of loading, place of unloading)
Ireland	Shipping manifests – be able to look up ferry sailings into and out of Ireland and see what operators (including vehicle registration numbers) are on it to enable better targeting. To have access to tolling data for tracing a route or routes are particular vehicle took prior to any encounter with our officers. And indeed, PTI data for any EU registered vehicle

Country	KEYSTONE is defining standard API for allowing logistic operators to share their data with authorities. What data are you more interested in?
Latvia	Cargo accompanying documents, driving licences, licences, vehicle registration and insurance, tachograph inspections
Lithuania	Information about Transport Companies/Managers from other countries (e.g., managers contacts).
Luxembourg	Evidence of transport operations carried out in the host Member State such as tachograph records, employment contract, drivers' timesheets, payslips and proof of payment.
Netherlands	Data over transport permits
Norway	Prior crimes/discrepancies, intelligence about the driver, hauliers and other parties
Poland	---
Portugal	Search for vehicle documents (licenses), documents related to the transportation of goods (transport manifests and others) and driver documents (driver's licenses and driver certificates). Logistic operators' entry and exit times for the purposes of controlling driving and rest times. Waybills and goods transported. Transport company. Destination of goods
Slovakia	---
Spain	Compulsory documentation under the provisions of both national and international regulations about transport and tachograph matters
Sweden	---
Switzerland	Holder data, driver data and company data

Enforcement authorities were also asked to identify the essential features and functionalities that KEYSTONE should include to enhance its utility and streamline their daily operations. Respondents emphasized the need for a centralized, multilingual, and user-friendly platform that provides real-time access to critical transport data. KEYSTONE should integrate all existing platforms into a single-entry point, ensuring seamless interoperability across EU Member States and third countries. This unified system should enable enforcement officers to quickly and efficiently verify key transport data, including loading and unloading points, consignment notes (CMRs), community licenses, and the validity of periodic technical inspections (PTIs) for all European vehicles.

A key requirement is the ability to retrieve maximum data with minimal effort. By simply entering a vehicle registration number, enforcement officers should be able to access comprehensive information on the operating company, community licenses, risk ratings, and CMR details. Similarly, driver-related data - including employment contracts, driving licenses, CPC qualifications (Code 95), and driver cards- should be readily accessible. The platform should also facilitate tracking truck and trailer movements, including border and ferry crossings, to enhance enforcement of cabotage and posting controls regulations.

Real-time data availability is essential to ensuring faster and more efficient roadside inspections, supported by automated cross-checking capabilities that link multiple databases, log data modifications, and maintain transparency by recording changes and identifying the responsible users. Additionally, a digital document management system should allow for the secure storage and retrieval of transport-related documents, reducing inspection times while ensuring the reliable handling of transport, vehicle, and driver data. For dangerous goods transport, the platform should provide emergency response information and safety instructions.

KEYSTONE must be accessible via tablets and mobile devices, ensuring easy use by law enforcement officers in the field. It should feature multilingual functionality to accommodate users from different countries and support real-time communication with other authorities. A single sign-on system -preferably using

national electronic identification (such as MitID)- would simplify access and authentication across different databases.

To enhance usability, KEYSTONE should be intuitive, even for non-specialized users, and offer the capability to generate official certified reports that can serve as legal evidence for transport violations. Finally, the system must be built on a robust legal and regulatory framework to ensure reliability, security, and full compliance with EU transport laws.

Table 23 provides a summary of responses from each country.

Table 23. Essential features or functionalities that KEYSTONE should have to be truly useful and facilitate daily work by country

Country	What essential features or functionalities do you think KEYSTONE should have to be truly useful and facilitate your daily work?
Austria	Loading and unloading points, shorter GNNS Data points
Belgium	Put all the platforms together with one access
Bulgaria	Possibility to check: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Community licenses issued in all European countries. • Validity period of a passed periodic technical inspection of road vehicles from all European countries. • Consignment notes (the CMR) for tracking the route of movement of trucks or combinations of trucks (tractor) and attached trailer/semi-trailer
Croatia	---
Denmark	Information must be "locked", so that if changes are made these are going to be logged. You need to be able to see who made the changes and check the previously registered information. A single point entry to all EU systems, preferably with the use of 'MitId' (national electronic identification)
Estonia	To get maximum data from minimum actions. For example- by the vehicle registration number, will be provided data about the operating company (community licence), CMR information, vehicle registration information. Risk rating. By checking driver, u can see employment contract or company employed to, driving licence and code 95 information, citizenship, drivers card and so on. This requires regulations that establish functionalities and rules.
Finland	---
Greece	Real time data, faster and better control. Easy connection via tablet to every law enforcement officer
Hungary	Authenticity, reliability, up to date Digital document management (e.g. transport document, vehicle data, driver data, etc.) can reduce the amount of time spent on inspections. For the transport of dangerous goods, the management of emergency information and instructions for safe intervention can also be important. Managing information on the dangerous goods being transported (e.g. safety data sheet).
Ireland	Information being available in multiple languages so enforces can use it
Latvia	Initial information on KEYSTONE seems to create a transparent working environment for control bodies in the field of international transport.
Lithuania	Real time communication with other authorities
Luxembourg	It should also be accessible for third countries
Netherlands	---
Norway	Availability
Poland	---
Portugal	Having all the information available in a single directory, for easy access and consultation. Details of the driver (identification, driving license, cqm, last tachograph card issued), the vehicle, the transport company (license, community license, vehicle license), the waybill to which it corresponds on the date

Country	What essential features or functionalities do you think KEYSTONE should have to be truly useful and facilitate your daily work?
	and time of the inspection, place of destination, border and ferry crossings, detachments of drivers to which it belongs.
Slovakia	--
Spain	A comprehensive access platform to all the different databases, with a single username and password. Make it intuitive and easy to handle even for non-specialized users. That allows obtaining printed reports to attach them, where appropriate, to complaints for violation of transport regulations and that serve as compelling evidence because they are certified by official organizations.
Sweden	--
Switzerland	Access to EUCARIS data in real time

Enforcement authorities were consulted on potential improvements to roadside inspections. They emphasized the need for a fully digitalized, integrated, and real-time data access system. A centralized, EU-wide platform consolidating all relevant databases into a single-entry point would greatly enhance efficiency, enabling instant retrieval of comprehensive information on hauliers, vehicles, and drivers without requiring multiple separate queries. They stressed the importance of accessing roadside inspection data from all EU countries and ensuring real-time connectivity with all available databases.

Currently, data-sharing inconsistencies between Member States present a major challenge to effective roadside inspections. Some countries do not contribute data to platforms such as EUCARIS, restricting access to essential information on vehicle registration, insurance, and technical inspection. Enforcement authorities stressed the need for standardized data contributions from all Member States to ensure full transparency. Additionally, real-time access to border crossing data, including queue lengths, crossing times, and driver details, would further enhance enforcement capabilities.

To improve roadside inspections, authorities propose the implementation of remote vehicle plates scanning combined with automated data analysis. A pre-screening system using number plate recognition cameras, drones, and GPS tracking of consignments would allow officers to assess risks before stopping a vehicle. Integration enforcement systems with road tolling and compliance monitoring platforms across Member States would also facilitate driving and resting time checks. Furthermore, establishing a standardized format for roadworthiness tests, accessible to all Member States, would contribute to a more transparent and consistent enforcement framework.

Coordination and training are also identified as key priorities. Authorities advocate for stronger collaboration among agencies responsible for heavy vehicle inspections to ensure a specialized and harmonized approach. Expanding training programs and increasing the workforce with qualified personnel are essential to meet the sector's growing demands. Institutional support is necessary to strengthen cross-border enforcement and develop a more structured operational framework for inspections.

A single, Europe-wide enforcement platform should offer mobile document verification, real-time tachograph data retrieval, and automated checklists to streamline inspections. The system should also generate automated alerts for non-compliance, flagging expired documents, missing waybills, or route deviations inconsistent with declared destinations. Norway's VaDIS digital roadside inspection tool is cited as a model system, effectively integrating with key databases and automatically reporting infringements. Future developments should ensure interoperability with eFTI, RESPER, and other relevant EU systems to enhance data exchange and enforcement efficiency.

Additionally, enforcement authorities stress the need for direct, real-time digital access to all relevant EU enforcement systems, including Europol, to strengthen roadside inspections. A quick digital notifications

system for infractions detected during roadside checks should be implemented across Europe. Lastly, authorities underscore the urgent need to enforce fines on foreign drivers, ensuring that penalties are effectively applied across borders.

Table 24 presents country-specific recommendations for improving roadside inspection procedures.

Table 24. Suggestion for improving the roadside inspections

Country	Do you have any suggestion for improving the roadside inspection (Digital system, process of check, etc.)?
Austria	---
Belgium	---
Bulgaria	---
Croatia	The ability to view all data from roadside checks conducted across the EU and insight in all available databases.
Denmark	Combining more digital data into a single data source with one entry point would significantly improve the efficiency of roadside checks. Such a system should include functionalities that ensure inquiries about a haulier, vehicle, or driver retrieve all relevant information from the appropriate registers in one step, eliminating the need to make the same inquiry across multiple registers to obtain the necessary data for a fully informed inspection.
Estonia	The lack of data provision by some Member States to shared databases. For instance, Poland does not contribute data to EUCARIS, and few Member States provide public access to vehicle registration, insurance, and technical inspection details. There is also a need for information about border crossings with third countries, including historical data on queue lengths, precise crossing times, and driver identification. While Estonia offers direct access to such border crossing data, obtaining similar information from other countries often requires phone calls or emails, with responses sometimes taking several days.
Finland	---
Greece	Remote scanning of vehicle plates and automatic data analysis.
Hungary	A list of documents related to specific shipments, coupled with a checklist to assist the verification process. The enforcement of driving and resting time rules could be significantly improved by enabling queries of vehicle pass data from other Member States' Road toll or enforcement systems. A pre-screening system utilizing number plate recognition cameras (including installed systems and drones) would allow for data collection on transport or vehicles before the actual check begins. Additionally, a GPS-based system for tracking consignments would provide real-time visibility of vehicle movements.
Ireland	Any improvements being considered on our side relate to sanctions which is a Member State competence, but anything that can speed up the time taken for our officers to complete a check would be welcome.
Latvia	Roadworthiness tests should be standardized into a uniform format that is accessible to controlling authorities across all Member States. This would not only facilitate the day-to-day work of enforcement officers but also create a more transparent environment for drivers, carriers, and control authorities alike.
Lithuania	---
Luxembourg	We are actively working to enhance training programmes both nationally and internationally, equipping our teams with the necessary skills. Concurrently, we are expanding our workforce by recruiting new, qualified personnel. We aim to improve coordination between the various entities involved in heavy vehicle inspections, fostering a more specialized and coordinated approach. This strategy will enable us to establish an effective operational framework for road transport inspections over time. Additionally, we are seeking increased institutional support.

Country	Do you have any suggestion for improving the roadside inspection (Digital system, process of check, etc.)?
Netherlands	A unified, shared system implemented across Europe. This system should incorporate clear and rapid digital notifications when infractions are detected during RSI anywhere in Europe, particularly for vehicles registered in the Netherlands
Norway	Ensuring direct and real-time digital access to all relevant EU systems, including Europol, during roadside inspections is crucial for effective enforcement. Norway's digital roadside inspection tool, VaDIS, exemplifies an advanced approach by integrating with key databases such as ERRU, Tachonet, and AUTOSYS, enabling inspection officers to efficiently retrieve necessary information. VaDIS securely stores all inspection data and automatically reports infringements to various relevant authorities, including ERRU, the risk rating system, the Norwegian National Collection Agency, and the Norwegian Labour Inspection Authority. The system also generates inspection reports for drivers and transport operators. Looking ahead, VaDIS is slated to integrate with eFTI, RESPER, and other relevant systems to further enhance the collection and exchange of critical roadside inspection data.
Poland	---
Portugal	A single, integrated platform should be established to consolidate all necessary information for enforcement actions in road transport. This platform would provide standardized guidelines for roadside checks, enabling real-time access to information without reliance on paper documents and ensuring the validity of required documentation. Key functionalities of the platform should include mobile document verification for digital consultation and validation of transport documents, real-time data collection through integration with tachograph systems for automatic retrieval of driving and rest period data, automated checklists generating pre-filled inspection forms requiring minimal manual input, and automated alerts for non-compliance to flag irregularities such as expired documentation, missing waybills, or route deviations inconsistent with declared destinations.
Slovakia	Solve the problem with the enforceability of fines imposed on foreign drivers
Spain	---
Sweden	---
Switzerland	---

5. CONCLUSIONS

Transport is a cornerstone of the EU economy, supporting millions of jobs and ensuring the smooth movement of goods and people. However, the sector faces pressing challenges, including climate change, digitalization gaps, and the need for more efficient enforcement of regulations. The KEYSTONE project aims to address these challenges by enhancing data accessibility and interoperability for enforcement authorities. Through real-time digital data exchange, KEYSTONE seeks to streamline inspections, improve regulatory compliance, and reduce administrative burdens for both businesses and authorities.

The introduction of electronic freight transport information (eFTI) under EU Regulation 2020/1056 represents a major step forward digital transformation, promising increased efficiency, transparency, and significant cost savings across the logistics sector. By integrating standardized, paperless solutions, KEYSTONE aligns with the EU's vision for a modern, secure, and sustainable transport ecosystem, strengthening the internal market's resilience and competitiveness.

A KEYSTONE survey (September 2023 - March 2024, Work Package 1) revealed that 76% of logistics operators, 100% of rail terminals, and 88% of competent authorities acknowledge the critical role of data and technology in improving compliance controls (Eftychia Koliou, Sabino Metta , & Alexeis Garcia Perez, 2024). This highlights the growing importance of digital innovation in transport enforcement.

This Deliverable D4.1, "Process and procedure report based on the concrete use cases", compares existing enforcement procedures and assess the operability of pilot implementations for enforcement authorities, particularly the police. The findings focus on roadside enforcement challenges and opportunities, emphasizing data accessibility and interoperability, digital platforms, verification processes, and potential improvements in enforcement efficiency. The key findings and conclusions are outlined below:

1. Key findings on roadside inspections:

- National Enforcement Plans: Virtually all participating countries implement an annual National Plan outlining specific actions and guidelines for road inspections.
- Inspection duration: A standard roadside check takes at least 30 minutes, but can last several hours depending on complexity, violations, and available enforcement personnel.
- Use of technology in inspections: Authorities extensively use devices to download, analyse, and transmit data from vehicle units or driver cards of digital tachographs to central databases and equipment to verify tachograph graphics. 81% of enforcement bodies utilize remote enforcement technologies like DSRC and REDCR, while 67% rely on the IMI System for cross-border enforcement.

2. Key findings regarding digital platforms for transport enforcement in the EU:

- Primary platforms for data exchange include TACHOnet (71% of responders), IMI (67% of responders), EUCARIS (57% of responders), and ERRU (57% of responders). Only one respondent reported using eFTI platforms.
- Access and Usage Issues: Not all enforcement entities or officers within the same country have full access to available platforms or the data stored within them. Permissions vary depending on the responsibilities of each authority. In most all cases, roadside enforcement officers' platforms through electronic applications, using credentials provided by IT departments.

- **System Fragmentation and Response Times:**
 - Most digital platforms operate independently, requiring officers to query multiple systems for comprehensive compliance checks.
 - Only one-third of authorities have a single-access point, underscoring system fragmentation.
 - While most queries receive real-time responses, some systems experiences delays of up to several days, depending on system availability, operator, and actual network coverage.
- More than half of the respondents (67%) consider these electronic applications and platforms valuable for enforcement checks on both national and foreign transport operators. They also indicated that they utilize the same application or platform for monitoring both categories of operators, ensuring consistency and efficiency in compliance verification.
- **Barriers to effective enforcement include:**
 - **Lack of Awareness and Training:** Road users and enforcement officers lack sufficient training on digital enforcement tools. The uncertainty about the legal validity of electronic documents deters broader adoption. Additionally, change management poses another obstacle, as the adoption of new tools often requires a transformation of internal processes.
 - **Multiple separate platforms,**
 - Each platform requires different access credentials.
 - Officers must switch multiple systems to access essential information and conduct multiple searches across various databases.
 - Databases access is often restricted or requires authorization from multiple administrative bodies.
 - **Inconsistencies in Data Usage Across Member States:** Variability in data enter, format and structures make difficult to interpret and compare information. Limited real-time access to enforcement databases weakens roadside checks.
 - **Complex and non-user-friendly systems** discourage engagement, with many users preferring traditional enforcement methods over digital alternatives.
 - **Inconsistent cross-border cooperation, harmonized procedures and differing legal frameworks.**
- **Authorities strongly advocate for the development of a single, integrated platform with controlled access tailored to each Member State's competence and responsibilities.** This system would consolidate relevant enforcement databases, streamline roadside inspections, and facilitate real-time document verification.

3. Key findings on data verification methods:

- **Inconsistencies in verification procedures.** Enforcement authorities employ varied verification methods, ranging from exclusively visual inspection of driver-presented documents to digital platform checks.

Additional verification methods include email or phone inquiries, national databases, and intelligence cooperation. However, access to these tools is inconsistent, leading to enforcement gaps.

- Limited access to information on transport companies and managers from other countries. Many enforcement agencies lack direct access to critical digital databases, restricting their ability to verify foreign transport operators and driver credentials. Among authorities with access, the most common method is consulting national electronic registers via ERRU platform. However, only six out of twelve surveyed countries actively use ERRU for these checks, indicating inconsistent application.
- The verification of transport company information varies among enforcement authorities, depending on operational procedures and available tools. While most checks occur during roadside inspections, some authorities extend verification process beyond roadside controls, conducting pre- and post-inspection inquiries.
- Documentation and processing of infringements: 48% of respondents use a combination of paper and digital forms to document and process infringements.
- Authorities face several operational challenges, including delays in document retrieval (reported by 81% of respondents), the reliance on manual inspections (76% of respondents), the need to consult multiple verification systems (71% of respondents), the inability to inspect trucks without stopping them (48% of respondents), and the lack of real-time data about flow of truck on the road to setup the check points. Language barriers and jurisdictional limitations on stopping vehicles also restrict effective control measures.
- Despite some progress in digital enforcement, with certain authorities adopting electronic platforms, many still rely on paper-based methods.

Enforcement authorities have identified several **challenges** in conducting effective roadside inspections:

- Real-time, integrated access to transport data. There is an urgent need for seamless, standardized cross-border data sharing covering vehicles, drivers, cargo, and companies. Ensuring compliance with legal and security requirements is essential for effective enforcement.
- Cargo and logistics information. Authorities require access to loading and unloading points, cargo documentation (CMRs, waybills, manifests), and hazardous goods (ADR) details. Tracking cargo at the pallet level and monitoring semi-trailer and towing unit movements would improve oversight of cabotage and posting regulations.
- Driver and employment data. Essential driver-related information includes licenses, employment contracts, professional certifications, tachograph records, and past infractions. Authorities also seek access to evidence of transport operations, such as time sheets, payslips, and proof of payment, to verify compliance with labour and social regulations.
- Vehicle and fleet tracking. There is a need to link vehicle registration and chassis numbers to owners and prior traffic offenses. Access to periodic technical inspection (PTI) data, tolling records, ferry manifests, insurance details, and real-time vehicle movement tracking would enhance enforcement efficiency.
- Company and compliance information. Enforcement officers require access to electronic contact details of transport managers, records of third-country transport operations, and company compliance

histories, including previous infractions. Intelligence on hauliers and key stakeholders would support targeted enforcement efforts.

- Secure and legally regulated data sharing. The establishment of a centralized, legally regulated platform integrating all relevant transport data would enhance enforcement efficiency, strengthen cross-border cooperation and ensure a harmonized and effective EU-wide transport control system.

Respondents emphasized the critical need for a centralized, digitalized, and real-time enforcement platform to streamline roadside inspections and enhance regulatory compliance. The KEYSTONE project is developing a standardized API to facilitate seamless transport data sharing between operators and enforcement authorities. Authorities recommend that the KEYSTONE platform should:

- Serve as a centralized, multilingual, accessibility and user-friendly system.
 - Single-entry point: KEYSTONE should serve as a single-entry point integrating all existing transport enforcement platforms across the EU and third countries. It must provide real-time access to critical transport data through a seamless and user-friendly manner.
 - Automated data cross-referencing: KEYSTONE should automatically verify and cross-check data across multiple databases, ensuring accuracy, track modifications, and logging changes for full transparency.
 - Mobile Accessibility: The platform must be accessible via tablets and mobile devices.
 - Multilingual interface: Enabling efficient cross-border cooperation.
- Real-time, comprehensive and automated data retrieval functionalities
 - Immediate access to transport, driver, and vehicle data: By entering a vehicle registration number, enforcement officers should instantly retrieve company details, community licenses, risk ratings, consignment notes (CMRs), driver-related data, including employment contracts, driving licenses, CPC qualifications (Code 95), and driver cards.
 - Truck and Trailer Tracking: The system should monitor vehicle movements, including border crossings and multimodal transits, improving oversight of cabotage and posting compliance.
 - Digital document management: Securely storing transport documents in a digital format to reduce inspection times.
 - Real-time communication: Enabling instant information exchange between enforcement authorities.
 - Automated Compliance Alerts: KEYSTONE should generate real-time alerts for non-compliance, flagging expired documents, missing waybills, and unauthorized route deviations.
- Be secure, legal compliance, and intuitive design
 - Single login system: Ensuring simplified and secure access for entities.
 - User-friendly interface: Designed to be intuitive and accessible for both specialists and non-specialists.

- Certified reports for legal evidence: The system should generate official, legally recognized reports.
- Strong legal and regulatory framework: Ensuring data security, compliance, and reliability.

The findings of this delivery highlight the urgent need for improved data accessibility, digital enforcement processes, and cross-border cooperation within the EU transport sector. Despite progress in digital transformation, several obstacles continue to hinder the effective use of existing data exchange platforms. The primary barriers to the effective use of these platforms include system fragmentation, technological limitations, administrative inefficiencies, and a lack of awareness and trust. To overcome these obstacles, all administrations must ensure their systems are capable of processing electronic documentation and are harmonized with cross-border enforcement platforms. A coordinated effort is essential to enhance interoperability across the EU, harmonize legal and technical frameworks for enforcement authorities, increase training and awareness for enforcement officers and transport operators, and simplify access to transport compliance data.

The introduction of a fully digital, real-time, and standardized EU-wide inspection system would significantly improve enforcement efficiency by reducing inspection times and administrative burdens. It will also ensure better compliance as authorities would have immediate access to verified data, allowing them to make informed enforcement decisions. Furthermore, such a system would foster better coordination among Member States, strengthening enforcement efforts across borders and contributing to a safer and more sustainable transport system.

In this context, the KEYSTONE digital solution is developing a standardised API to streamline transport data sharing between operators and enforcement authorities. The platform will function as a centralized, multilingual, and user-friendly system, integrating all existing transport enforcement platforms across the EU and third countries. By enabling instant access to transport, driver, and vehicle data, it will significantly improve enforcement efficiency. The platform will employ automated cross-referencing with multiple databases to ensure transparency and data accuracy. KEYSTONE will offer several essential features as mobile accessibility, real-time tracking of truck and trailer movements, digital document management, and seamless communication with other authorities. A single-login system, strong legal compliance, and an intuitive design will ensure secure access, data protection, and ease of use for both specialized and non-specialized users.

Through KEYSTONE, each country will maintain its national enforcement system while benefiting from a harmonized interfaces and standardized data models. This approach will standardize data-sharing across Member States, strengthen enforcement mechanisms, and modernize roadside inspection procedures to create a fairer, safer, and more efficient EU transport sector. The integration of transport data across the EU through KEYSTONE represents a significant step forward in the digital transformation of enforcement procedures. By creating a system that delivers greater value than isolated national solutions, this initiative will enhance enforcement capabilities, improve regulatory compliance, and support the EU's broader goals of creating a more secure, efficient, and sustainable transport network.

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Annex 1: Questionnaire

The following contains the questionnaire distributed to various control authorities across several European countries.

Keystone's digital solutions will accelerate the data sharing between logistics operators and transport enforcement authorities based on a federated approach.

The **purpose** of this survey is to understand the current practices used by authorities enforcing EU road transport rules to collect and/or verify data on drivers / vehicles/ transport companies that are both from their own European country and from other EU Member States.

At the EU level several platforms exist to facilitate this data exchange, prominent among these are **RESPER** (EU Driving License Networ), **TACHONET** (Network for Tachograh Cards) and **ERRU** (European Register of road Transport Undertakings).

KEYSTONE aims to develop an aplication to facilitate cross-border enforcement and ease the process of obtaining relevant data.

When enforcement open KEYSTONE application they will have access to:

Logistic data (information of the goods and their movement)

Easier access to driver, company and vehicle data.

Accordingly, **the survey seeks to understand the process** currently employed by enforcement authorities to collect and/or verify data while conducting checks on drivers / vehicles / transport companies from other EU Member States.

To test KEYSTONE technology in a real enviroment, **two pilots** will be developed

Funded by the European Union

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Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Entity name: _____ **Country:** _____

Which kind of enforcement authorities describes you better?

- Customs
 Finance police
 Ministry
 Road police
 Public authority (e.g. sea port authority)
 Other

CONTROL:

1. Does your country have a Road Transport Inspection Plan that establishes actions and guidelines to follow during roadside inspection?

- Yes
 No

If yes:

What is the name of the plan?	
What entity approves the plan?	
What is the frequency of the plan?	
Where may it be consulted?	

2. Average time taken to complete a roadside inspection: _____

3. Which are the main technical & telematic means you currently use for carrying out the controls and compliance checks? (tick as many boxes as necessary)

- | | |
|--------------------------|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Equipment capable of downloading data from the vehicle unit: (please specify the technology used) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Equipment capable of downloading data from the driver card of the digital tachograph, reading data, and analysing data and/or transmitting findings to a central database for analysis, and if relevant equipment to check the tachograph sheets: (please specify the technology used) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Remote interrogation equipment (Remote early detection communication reader DSRC/REDCR) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Information system for the single market (the IMI) -for the enforcement of the posting of drivers and tackling letterbox companies |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Digital platforms |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Other: (add as many as necessary) |

DIGITAL PLATFORMS

4. Which digital platforms do you use for sharing and/or retrieving data? (tick as many boxes as necessary)

- | | | | | |
|--|--|---|---------------------------------|-----------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> DEFRA | <input type="checkbox"/> DVSA | <input type="checkbox"/> eFTI platforms | <input type="checkbox"/> ERRU | <input type="checkbox"/> EUCARIS |
| <input type="checkbox"/> IMI | <input type="checkbox"/> IPAFFS | <input type="checkbox"/> PSC | <input type="checkbox"/> RESPER | <input type="checkbox"/> TACHOnet |
| <input type="checkbox"/> TRACES | <input type="checkbox"/> Other: (add as many as necessary) | | | |
| <input type="checkbox"/> I do not use any digital platform | | | | |

5. In the event you use a digital platform, do you have direct access to it?

- | | |
|--------------------------|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Yes, as an officer responsible for roadside inspection, I can directly access the platform |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | No, I need to make a request to another colleague/department who has access to the platform. |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Other, please explain. |

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6. How do you connect to the platform?

- I connect to it via an electronic application, by using credentials provided by my IT department
- Connection to it is established by another colleague/department.
- Other, please explain:

7. In the event you use different digital platforms,

	YES	NO
Is the process to connect to them the same?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Each one has its own registry (user name and password)?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Can you connect them through a single entry point?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

8. How long does it take to receive a response to your query on the platform you use.

- It works in real-time
- Other, please indicate:

9. Are these electronic applications/platforms helpful for conducting checks for both domestic and non-domestic transport operators.

- Yes, we use the same electronic application/platform for both domestic and non-domestic transport operators. Please provide the name and the data it helps you collect:

Please also explain if this electronic platform or application has links with RESPER, TACHONET and ERRU and if so, how does this link work:

- No, we use different electronic applications/platforms for domestic and non-domestic transport operators. Please provide the names and the data these applications/platforms help you collect.

Please also explain if the electronic application/platform used for international transport operators has links with RESPER, TACHONET and ERRU and if so, how does this link work.

- We do not use any electronic application/platform.

10. In your opinion, What are the main challenges or barriers that prevent existing data-sharing platforms from being truly effective and widely used?

11. What specific user needs or use cases are not addressed by existing data-sharing platforms?

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VERIFYING DATA

12. How do you verify the driving licenses and competence certificates (Driver CPC) presented by a driver who is not from your country?

- I make a phone call or email the concerned authority in another country that issued the license/certificate.
- I use the EU Driving License Network (RESPER).
- I trust the information presented to me by the driver and do not make any verification.
- Other, please explain.
- I do not carry out this check

13. How do you verify the validity of a driver's tachograph card.

- I make a phone call or email the concerned authority in another country that issued the card
- I use the TACHONET platform
- I trust the information presented to me by the driver and do not make any verification
- Other, please explain:
- I do not carry out this check

14. Can you access information on Transport Companies/Managers from other countries (e.g., information on community licenses, certificates of professional competence and past infringements)?

- Yes No

If yes, how do you access this information?

- I usually send a request for this information to other countries via email.
- I consult the national electronic registers of other countries via ERRU platform.
- Other, please explain.

15. When do you verify this information?

- Prior to a roadside check
- During the roadside check
- After the roadside check
- Other, please explain:
- I do not carry out this check

16. If you detect an infraction during the control, you would file the infringement using

- Paper forms
- Telematics data (please specify the technology used):
- Combination

17. What are your main challenges during the control inspection? (tick as many boxes as necessary)

- Paper documents that consumes lot of time for checking because the data must be inteserted manually in the different systems
- Needs to connects lot of different systems to check all information
- Needs to wait for driver to provide all necessary information
- No possibility of checking truck without stopping them
- No data available aboutflow of truck on the road to setup the check points
- Other (add as many as necessary):

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THE FUTURE

18. KEYSTONE is defining standard API for allowing logistic operators to share their data with authorities. What data are you more interested in?

19. What essential features or functionalities do you think KEYSTONE should have to be truly useful and facilitate your daily work?

20. Do you have any suggestion for improving the roadside inspection (Digital system, process of check, etc.)?

Thank you very much for your participation.

We realize your time is of the essence.

Let's stay in touch

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